

PRMVS

Regional Wildlife Management Program for
Mesoamerica and the Caribbean

TRIENNIAL REPORT 1990-92

RESEARCH

OUTREACH

TRAINING

PROFESSIONAL STAFF 1990-92 with STUDENTS of IV and V PROMOTIONS

Front row sitting left to right: Claudette Mo, Carlos Salcedo, Jacobo Arauz, Cecilia Pacheco, Michael McCoy, Montserrat Carbonell, Emilio Vargas; 2nd row: Federico Chinchilla, Allan Marín, Eduardo Naranjo, Eduardo Carrillo, Victor Cartín, Chris Vaughan; 3rd row: Silvia Rodríguez, Miriam Carranza, Lilliana Araya, Mizonil Leitón, Emma Peñaranda, Hilda Casasola, Wilfredo Segura, Javier Beltran, Teresa Zuñiga; 4th row: Jorge Fallas, David Norman.

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"The Regional Wildlife Management Program for MesoAmerica and the Caribbean
represents the model our University is striving for. It combines the elements of
training, research and community outreach in a tangible manner."

-Rose Marie Rufz
President
National University
Heredia, COSTA RICA
(1990)

OVERVIEW

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The following summary lists most of the major accomplishments of The Regional Wildlife Management Program for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean (PRMVS), from 1990 to 1992.

OVERVIEW

- Twenty institutions provided funding for PRMVS;
- Cooperative agreements were signed with 15 institutions;
- Five institutions provided Fulbright, Sabbatical or Visiting Professors;
- Four institutions participated in cooperative training or exchange projects;
- Of our 27 graduates, 26 are presently involved in the cutting edge of conservation work from México to Patagonia;
- PRMVS has received the attention of eminent scientists, leaders of donating institutions, ministers, presidents and princes;

GRADUATE TRAINING PROGRAM

- Research and teaching staff consisted of 19 professors from six countries with National University positions, nine at the Ph.D. level and 10 with master's degrees. PRMVS also received the aid of 14 guest professors and researchers;
- Nine research assistants from six countries participated as research assistants and special students;
- Ten administrative staff hired by the National University participated;
- Fifty-two students from 15 Latin American countries have begun graduate studies, 25 have graduated, 15 are involved in thesis work, 10 are taking courses, and two left the program;
- Five students from two Latin American countries studied and completed their Licenciature degree in wildlife management;
- Forty-five thesis projects have been or are being carried out in 10 Latin American countries, in many cases as the first pioneering research carried out in that country on selected species or habitats;
- PRMVS graduates are assuming leadership roles in biodiversity-wildlife management programs throughout Latin America - with five directors or chiefs of wildlife agencies, 10-university professors, and a variety of other positions in NGOs and governmental agencies;

STAFF RESEARCH, MONITORING, MANAGEMENT AND OUTREACH

- Sixteen research projects by PRMVS staff are being carried out, oftentimes combined with thesis work. Some are important model wildlife management-biodiversity projects and all provide needed data on neotropical natural resource management;
- Seventy-two papers were given at international meetings in 13 countries, while 10 papers were presented at national events. Ten professors and 11 students participated;

- Ninety-six publications have been produced by PRMVS staff and students between 1987-1992, including 11 books or parts therein, 44 journal articles, 24 works produced by scientific meetings, and 17 technical reports;

OUTREACH THROUGH INFORMATION AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER

- BIODOC, the Wildlife Documentation Center, has accumulated over 3,000 book titles, completed collections of six scientific journals (Journal of Wildlife Management, Ecology, Journal of Mammalogy, Auk, Ecological Monographs, the Wilson Bulletin), and a partial collection of 270 other scientific journals and subscribes to 79 scientific journals;
- BIODOC has over 7,000 reprints of wildlife-related articles, as well as Wildlife Review Index 1971-92 on a databased CD-ROM disk. BIODOC also contains a complete copy of Wildlife Review (1935-92) and Zoological Record (1974-92) for birds, mammals, reptiles and amphibians.
- BIODOC has over 1,200 technical and institutional reports, and theses on file as gray literature;
- Over 6,500 users were served by BIODOC between 1988-1992;
- The Remote Sensing and Geographical Information System Laboratory (TELESIG) offers graduate courses, short-courses, and research possibilities, with the following equipment: three computers with 80486 processors of 33 and 50 Mhz equipped with high resolution video systems, 1.2 Gbyte hard disks, an Exabyte 8 mm tape system and 88 Mbyte Syquest removable disk system;
- Digital processing in TELESIG is possible through AGIS, DRAGON, IDRISI, OSU-MAP, and CI/SIG programs. A Summagraphics MicroGrid III digitizing table of 1.44 by 1.12 meters is available for entering data, and an HP XL-300 color laser printer for map output;
- Microcomputer facilities include 18 microcomputers, three laptop portable micros for use in the field. All staff and students are computer-literate, receiving training and refresher courses;
- The re-initiation of the international journal, *Vida Silvestre Neotropical*, discontinued after four numbers in 1990, was awarded to PRMVS by a consortium of financing conservation organizations. Production has begun in 1993.
- Eight documentary films based on original research for a total of 150 minutes and two slide shows of 25 minutes duration about PRMVS were produced;
- Over 100 seminars, seven short-courses and 19 workshops were given by 12 professors between 1988-1992.

FINANCIAL SUPPORT 1987-1992

- Eighteen donors and the National University have contributed a total of \$3,050,350 to PRMVS;
- Donations have included: staff salaries, student scholarships, research, general services, equipment, BIODOC, a student residence building and foundation administrative overhead;
- Major funding agencies have been: United States Fish and Wildlife Service, World Wildlife Fund-US, German Academic Exchange Program, Organization of American States, John and Catherine MacArthur Foundation, and Jessie Smith Noyes Foundation.

PARTICIPATING INSTITUTIONS

Provided Funding Donations for PRMVS

Agency for International Development, Washington, D.C. (AID-US)
Audubon Society, Fairfax Chapter, Fairfax, Virginia
Conservation International, Washington, D.C. (CI)
Douroucouli Foundation, Los Angeles, California
Earth Island Institute, San Francisco, California
German Academic Exchange Program, Berlin, Germany (DAAD)
International Council for Bird Preservation, Washington, D.C. (CIPA)
International Treaty on Commercialization of Species, (CITES)
Jesse Smith Noyes Foundation, New York, New York
John and Catherine MacArthur Foundation, Chicago, Illinois
National Council for Scientific Research and Technology, San José, Costa Rica (CONICIT)
Organization for Tropical Studies, Durham, North Carolina (OET)
Organization of American States, Washington, D.C. (OEA)
Organization for Migrations, United Nations, Geneva, Switzerland (OIM)
Phoenix Foundation, Tucson, Arizona
Program for Studies in Tropical Conservation, University of Florida, Gainesville, Florida (PSTC)
Project Lighthawk, Santa Fe, New Mexico
United States Fish and Wildlife Service, Washington, D.C. (USFWS)
Wildlife Conservation International, New York, New York (WCI)
World Wildlife Fund-US, Washington, D.C. (WWF-US)

Cooperative Agreements signed with PRMVS or UNA

Colorado State University, Fort Collins, Colorado
Costa Rican Wildlife Service, San José, Costa Rica
Data Delta Systems, Inc., Picayune, Mississippi
German Academic Exchange Program, Berlin, Germany
Green Iguana Foundation, San José, Costa Rica
Lethbridge Community College, Lethbridge, Alberta, Canada
Middle Tennessee University, Murfreesboro, Tennessee
Oregon State University, Corvallis, Oregon
Organization for Tropical Studies, Durham, North Carolina
School for Field Studies, Beverly, Massachusetts
United States Fish and Wildlife Service, Washington, D.C.
University Alcalá de Henares, Madrid, Spain
University of Idaho, Moscow, Idaho
University of Wisconsin, Madison, Wisconsin
World Wildlife Fund-US, Washington, D.C.

Provided Fulbright, Sabbatical or Visiting Professors

Lethbridge Community College, Lethbridge, Alberta, Canada
Montana State University, Bozeman, Montana
Oregon State University, Corvallis, Oregon
Organization for Migrations, United Nations, Geneva, Switzerland
University of Idaho, Moscow, Idaho

Cooperative Projects (training, exchange, etc.)

Bat Conservation International, Austin, Texas
Clemson University, Clemson, South Carolina
Organization for Tropical Studies, Durham, North Carolina
University of Massachusetts, Amherst, Massachusetts
Welder Wildlife Foundation, Sinton, Texas

OUR HISTORY AND INTERNATIONAL MISSION

The mission of the *Regional Wildlife Management Program for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean (PRMVS)* is to provide a body of well-trained professionals in the wildlife-biodiversity-natural resource field who will plan, develop and carry out research, extension (outreach), teaching and management projects in Latin America. Many wildlife-biodiversity management problems must be addressed on a hemispheric-wide basis because; a) much of the biodiversity is shared by countries, b) funding is limited, c) biodiversity destruction is accelerating and d) technical training is most efficiently carried out regionally. For these reasons and to develop such coordination, the heads of governmental wildlife institutions from Panama, Costa Rica, Nicaragua, Honduras, El Salvador, Guatemala, and the Dominican Republic and two funding agencies, the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) and the World Wildlife Fund-US (WWF-US), unanimously approved the formation in Costa Rica of the *PRMVS* during a regional meeting held in Panama in October, 1984. The pledged support of *PRMVS* by National University (UNA) officials, the incredible biological diversity in such a small country, and the democratic traditions and history of political stability of Costa Rica played an important role in the decision. Finally, the important initial funding by USFWS and WWF-U.S., and the Organization of American States was essential in starting *PRMVS*.

Three regional priorities were identified during the Panama meeting: a) training at the graduate level "in situ", b) developing model wildlife-biodiversity projects, and c) outreach through regional information and technology transfer, including a wildlife documentation center. The UNA in Here-

To date, 52 students have entered our graduate program representing 15 Latin American countries. Over 25 graduates are now involved in the cutting edge of conservation work from Mexico to Patagonia...

dia, Costa Rica, was chosen to host this program because it has been a pioneer in Latin America in the development of programs in teaching, research and outreach in the field of neotropical wildlife management. Courses in wildlife and wildlands management were initiated with one professor in 1978 in

the School of Environmental Sciences for fourth-year forestry students at a B.Sc. level. In 1980 a second professor was added to this effort. From 1983 to

... by the year 2000, over 400 professional administrators and over 3,400 researchers, teachers and managers will be needed for wildlife and related programs in Latin America... (WWF report, 1980)

1987 a post-B.Sc. degree or "Licenciature" was carried out for seven forestry students interested in specializing in wildlife management. The fruits of this pioneering effort flowered into the current Master's degree program in wildlife management. Currently, 12 professors participate in the program on a permanent basis.

A report by WWF-US on training needs in Latin America in the natural resource field estimated that by the year 2000, over 400 professional administrators and over 3,400 researchers, teachers, and managers would be needed for wildlife and related programs. In addition, **Measure 83 of the Global Biodiversity Strategy** (published by World Resources Institute, International Union for Nature, and the United Nations Program for the Environment) calls for "increasing support for the training of professionals in biodiversity, especially in developing countries".

Since 1987, 52 students have entered our graduate program, representing 15 Latin American countries. Over 25 graduates are now involved in the cutting edge of conservation work from Mexico to Patagonia, as directors of governmental wildlife agencies, university professors, heads of NGOs, etc.

Research and management of wildlife-biodiversity resources, both by staff and former students, are showing others how to do it. Outreach projects include BIODOC, opened in 1987, and unsurpassed in Latin America as a first-class wildlife library, as well as the re-initiation of the scientific journal, "Vida Silvestre Neotropical", essential for Latin American wildlife scientists, managers, and administrators.

The present triennial report (1990-1992)(*our first!*) summarizes the accomplishments of *PRMVS* students and staff, as well as, funding and future directions that *PRMVS* will take into the next century. We are proud of our achievements to date, yet know that to reverse the natural resource destruction trends, we must work harder, and *PRMVS* must be ready to evolve into new directions and accept new challenges. ♡

LATIN AMERICA'S NEW LEADERS IN CONSERVATION: WHAT OUR GRADUATES ARE DOING NOW

We believe the success of PRMVS can be measured to a large degree by the professional activities of our 25 master's and 2 licenciature graduates who are presently working in 12 Latin American countries.

Juan Diego Alfaro (Costa Rica) is Chief of Research of La Amistad Biosphere Reserve in Costa Rica. He recently constructed a research station in Hitoy Cerere Biological Reserve.

José Luis Altuve (Venezuela) is a professor in the Graduate Program in Renewable Natural Resources in Aquatic and Wildlife Management, at the Experimental National University of the Western Plains, (UNELLEZ), Guanare, Venezuela. He currently is in charge of the Biodocumentation Center and curator of the museum. He also teaches courses in Zoology and Wildlife Inventory in the program. He recently (1991) represented UNELLEZ in a scientific expedition to the Amazons.

Marcelo Aranda (Mexico) is an Associate Researcher at the Institute of Ecology in Mexico. His research on jaguar food habits in the Calakmul Reserve is a continuation of his thesis work. In addition, he teaches Mammalogy and Wildlife and Wildland Management in the Ecology Master's Program of the Northeast University in Tampico, Tamaulipas. Marcelo has also been named Invited Professor (Wildlife Management and Conservation) of the Diploma Degree Program in Protected Areas, Conservation and Management in Latin America, organized by Ducks Unlimited, México (DUMAC). He is also directing three licenciature theses. Recently he

participated as Visiting Professor of the Field Course in Vertebrate Population Ecology given to the V Promotion students of PRMVS.

Never Bonino (Argentina) is Chief of the Ecology and Wildlife Management Group (1992) of the Bariloche Experimental Station which forms part of the National Institute of Agrarian Technology (INTA). In 1992 he gave the first course in Wildlife Management Techniques to the First Promotion at the new Master's Program in Wildlife Management at the National University in Cordoba, Argentina.

Christopher Vaughan

José Calvopiña (Ecuador) was named Director of the Department of Introduced Mammals at the Galápagos Biological Field Station upon his return to Ecuador in 1990. He now works in the Antisana Foundation and coordinates the management and development plan for the Condor Bioserve in Ecuador.

Eduardo Carrillo (Costa Rica) was named professor at PRMVS (1990) and teaches Introduction to Microcomputers and the Field Course in Vertebrate Population Ecology. Eduardo has participated in back-to-back practical training programs: a 3-month wildlife management program at Welder Wildlife Foundation in Sinton, Texas (1991), and with the Massachusetts Cooperative Wildlife Unit at the University of Massachusetts at Amherst (1992). In Costa Rica, he has participated as mammalogist in biota surveys of wildland areas, including Tortuguero, and Osa Peninsula.

Carlos Cerrato (Honduras), professor in the Biology Department of the Autonomous University of Honduras (UNAH) since 1979, has given new courses at UNAH: Wildlands Management, Natural Resource Management, and Research Methods. He has been active in research on wildlife and wildland projects in Honduras, both as a researcher and thesis advisor to licenciature students. He has been consulting with several

international organizations, PNUD, Environmental Program for Central America (PACA) and The Nature Conservancy. He is acting secretary of the Honduran Biologists Professional College. Carlos plans to continue graduate studies at the University of Florida in 1993.

Silvia Chalukian (Argentina) worked as Projects Director for FUNAM (Friends of Nature Foundation) in Santa Cruz, Bolivia, which is responsible for the management of various national parks and reserves. After four months, she was hired by a new institution responsible for management of a park in the Amazon jungle of Bolivia.

Alfredo Cuarón (Mexico) is continuing his graduate studies towards his doctorate at Cambridge University in England.

María José González (Guatemala) is advisor in the wildlife field to the Guatemalan Council of Protected Areas (CONAP), evaluating

projects presented to this entity and organizing the Flora and Fauna section. She also developed recent Guatemalan game hunting regulations and seasons. María José is the national coordinator of technical cooperation of the national parks network of FAO and administers the Ramsar Convention in her country. In addition to giving courses in Wildlife Management and General Ecology at the University of Valle, and acting as a thesis adviser in both the University of Valle, and San Carlos University, she has participated in a vertebrate research project in the Maya Biosphere Reserve in El Petén as part of the Panther Passage Project.

Iliá Hartasánchez (México) finished her thesis in December 1992 and is currently seeking employment. She plans a biological survey of the wetlands of Laguna Términos, Campeche, México.

Daniel Hernández (Costa Rica) works as a researcher in the Costa Rican National Museum and is currently developing several research projects

related to resident and migratory birds in Costa Rica: a database which currently holds 3400 records of biological information

and a monitoring project in two permanent Atlantic zone stations. He has seven scientific articles published or in press, several based on his thesis work, including a field guide on the aquatic vegetation of Palo Verde marsh. He is vice-president of the International Council for Bird Preservation, Costa Rican Chapter. He serves on the board of directors of the Costa Rican Biological Professionals College, as well as the Organization for Tropical Studies' (OTS) board of directors as the representative from the National Museum of Costa Rica. He also serves on OTS's nomination committee and scientific assessor committee for Palo Verde Field Station.

Oscar Lara (Guatemala) worked six months as a consultant with the Green Iguana Project in Costa Rica with Dagmar Werner during the preliminary analysis in the elaboration of a management plan for the Iguana Reserve. He is a professor at the University of San Carlos in Guatemala.

Eduardo Carrillo

Nancy López (Paraguay) was named Chief (1991) of the Fauna Division of the National Parks and Wildlife Service and the Biological Inventories Department of the National Museum of Paraguay. She has been very active in research and participation at national and international meetings, authoring over 14 scientific and popular articles and giving papers in 17 national, regional and international meetings in the United States, Europe and Latin America, many based on her master's work on psittacids. Finally, she is Secretariat for the V Neotropical Ornithology Congress to be held in Paraguay in 1995. She has remained active as a researcher and environmental educator. Nancy is also on the boards of several na-

tional and international ornithological and conservation organizations, including Vice President of The Paraguayan Biological Society, Paraguayan Representative for ICBP, and member of several "Species Survival Commissions" of the IUCN.

Leda Malavassi

(Costa Rica) works for the Pro-Zoo Foundation as general curator of Costa Rica's Simon Bolivar National Zoological Park. Her duties include: design of pens and cages, formulation of animal diets, control of animal histories, collaboration with a veterinary in animal health, elaboration of environmental education programs, and aids in the search for funding. She also coordinates field personnel and volunteers, the hand-rearing of orphaned animals that arrive, as well as, all research carried out at the zoo. She will soon receive a course in administration and management of aquariums and zoos in West Virginia, and a course in captive-rearing of reptiles and amphibians at the Baltimore Aquarium, Maryland.

Daniel Hernández

Ignacio March

(Mexico) was co-founder and is Vice President of ECOSFERA, a Mexican NGO which is working on environmental problems in southern Mexico. He has been actively involved in a campaign to protect the rights of the Lacandon Indians of the Montañas Azules. ECOSFERA recently joined efforts with two other NGOs and formed the Center for Ecological Research of the Southeast. Ignacio was given the position of "A" Researcher and is charged with the implementation of a Geographical Information System Laboratory (GISL) which will assist in classifying satellite images for different research and conservation projects in southeastern Mexico. Since his time with INIREB working with the Lacandon Mayans, Ignacio has been actively involved in projects which promote

indigenous rights in the Montañas Azules of Chiapas, the largest subtropical rainforest in Mexico. He was translator and coordinated a visit of two Lacandon Mayans to indigenous groups in the western United States in 1989, and has promoted research and sustainability projects with his friends. Since 1989, Ignacio has published six articles, has been thesis advisor in three licenciate theses, and has given over 15 talks in regional, national and international congresses, courses and meetings.

César Márquez (Colombia) is currently compiling a directory of conservation organizations (governmental and NGO's) of Colombia, financed by USFWS. He also has created a Colombian foundation dedicated to the conservation of tropical raptors. Funds are currently sought to research the management of Colombian raptors by region (Choco, Amazons, Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta, etc.).

Javier Monge (Costa Rica) worked three months as assistant researcher with the project, "Efficacy of mechanical alarm in the reduction of damage to irrigated rice by black-bellied whistling ducks in Guanacaste province, Costa Rica", with Michael McCoy. He also has been asked to prepare a course in Vertebrate Pest Analysis and Control for PRMVS and for the University of Costa Rica.

Sonia Navarro (México) works at the Biological Sciences Faculty at the University of Guadalajara where she teaches a course in Biology.

Miguel Rodríguez (Costa Rica, Licenciature) was named Director of the Wildlife Service of Costa Rica in 1990, and has been involved recently in a fund-raising program in collaboration with the Ding Darling Foundation, US. Funds are being raised by the sale of prints of an award-winning waterfowl painting by a Costa Rican artist. Miguel helped organize this contest. He has worked hard on the new wildlife regulations of Costa Rica and most recently helped organize an international workshop

to look into the problems and solutions of jaguar management in Latin America.

Joel Sáenz (Peru, Licenciature), while working on coatimundi research in Costa Rica, assisted in a documentary film with the British Broadcasting Corporation about the coatimundi in the tropical dry forest, which will be aired worldwide in early 1993. He is currently pursuing a master's degree in PRMVS as a student of the V Promotion.

Ronald Sánchez (Costa Rica) is professor of zoology and coordinates the biology course of studies at the San Ramón Regional Center of the University of Costa Rica in San Ramón, Costa Rica. He is representative in the technical committee of the Arenal Conservation Unit for the San Ramón Forest Reserve, administered by this university. He continues research on howler monkeys, which formed part of his thesis work.

Eduardo Velazco (Colombia) is Coordinator of the Data Center for Conservation of the Corporation of Cali Valley. This institution will implement management guidelines for the Farallones of Cali National Park in 1993. The same will be developed next year for Las Hermosas National Park in the central Cordillera. The Corporation will also manage waterfowl later this year in Laguna de Sonsa Natural Reserve.

Christopher Vaughan

Jorge Ventocilla (Panama) works as Coordinator of the Environmental Education Program at the Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute in Panama, and continues to coordinate several programs with the Kuna Indians, begun with his thesis.

Christopher Vaughan

Roberto Vides (Argentina) returned to his work at the National University of Tucumán and was responsible for direction of the Biological Park Sierra de San Javier, an area of

protected subtropical forest of "Yungas" of 14,000 ha, where he did his thesis work. He participated in the foundation of the "Ecology Research Laboratory of Yungas" along with Argentinean university biologists and CONICET. During 1992, with university funding, he carried out the first stage in the development of ecological indicators to evaluate environmental impact and wildlife management. He also completed his doctor's degree in biological sciences in his university on the structure and community dynamics of forest birds of "Yungas", oriented toward management and conservation. He currently works in Costa Rica as biologist for the Foundation Pro Green Iguana, with Dagmar Werner, with the responsibility to generate a management plan for the Iguana Reserve and related buffer zones.

Lilián Villalba (Bolivia) worked for four months in 1991 as Scientific Technical Coordinator of the Institute of Ecology in the project "Biodiversity and Ecosystem Conservation in the Protected Areas of Bolivia". Since early 1992, Lilián has worked as the Technical Coordinator of the General Directorate of Protected Areas (DNAP), part of the National Secretary of the Environment (SENMA) in Bolivia. Additionally, Lilián has taught wildlife management concepts in both The First Workshop/Course on Wildlife Conservation organized by the Institute of Ecology and the Second Course on Planning, Management and Protection of Indigenous Territories organized by the Center for Research and Documentation of Beni. Finally, Lilián has been active in national forums, debates and conferences discussing themes related to vicuñas and camelids in general; her thesis work.

Grace Wong (Costa Rica), after studying the ecology of the squirrel monkey (*Saimiri oerstedii*) for three years in Costa Rica, has joined forces with her husband, **Eduardo Carrillo** (Costa Rica) to organize a research project funded by PRMVS, The Phoenix Zoo, the Organization of American States and Conservation International to study and manage the squirrel monkey in the Manuel Antonio region of Costa Rica. In early 1993 she will give the course of Environmental Education and Communication to the V Promotion of PRMVS, and continue to work in PRMVS to promote the environmental education program.

IMPORTANT EVENTS AND VISITORS TO PRMVS

PRMVS has received the attention of eminent scientists, leaders of donating institutions, ministers, presidents and princes.

Prince Philip, Duke of Edinburgh, visited PRMVS on February 1, 1988 and officially inaugurated the Wildlife Documentation Center (BIODOC) with the participation of Dr. Carlos Araya Pochet, President of UNA, other university officials and visiting dignitaries. Prince Philip also met with the I and II Promotion students, professors and administrative staff of PRMVS.

Christopher Vaughan

The World Wildlife Fund-US Board of Directors during their participation at the IUCN meeting in San José, Costa Rica in February 1988, visited the installations of PRMVS and met the I and II Promotion students, professors and administrative staff. A short ceremony was held to commemorate WWF's participation in the development of PRMVS.

Both the Smithsonian Institution in Panama and the Green Iguana Foundation signed legal cooperative agreements with UNA on September 23, 1988 which permitted D. Werner to move a major part of her iguana project to Costa Rica and work out of PRMVS at UNA.

Ex-president of Costa Rica, Oscar Arias, Margarita Arias, ministers, diplomatic corps, UNA officials and PRMVS members visited D. Werner's green iguana project at Finca "La Avellana" February 22, 1990. Several hundred young iguanas were released to the wild, and the group lunched on captive-raised iguana meat. (Attendance 120).

Christopher Vaughan

Paul Erlich, respected ecologist from the University of California at Stanford lunched with III Promotion students March 4, 1990 and discussed the global environmental crisis. Dr. Erlich stressed the importance of a global approach to these problems, such as ozone depletion, climate change and natural resource abuse.

On March 6, 1990, 50 professionals attending a Central American regional graduate programs meeting, including directors and vice-presidents from Central American universities visited PRMVS and were accompanied by PRMVS Director, Christopher Vaughan and BIODOC coordinator, Enrique Quesada.

On August 17, 1990, Ing. Gregorio Contreras, Director of the Organization of American States in Costa Rica received

recognition for OEA's support to PRMVS since 1982. This support was crucial for PRMVS to begin functioning.

On December 6, 1990, the German Academic Exchange Program (DAAD) received recognition by PRMVS for their assistance providing student scholarships and German scholars. UNA President, Lic. Rose Marie Ruiz, Germany's Ambassador to Costa Rica, Dr. Dieter Zeisler, and DAAD's Director, Dr. Arnold Spitta as well as PRMVS staff and students were present for the ceremony.

During April 23-26, 1991, the First Latin American Conference Graduate Programs in Wildlife Management was held. Delegates from the wildlife management graduate programs Venezuela, Brazil and Argentina, and PRMVS staff and students as well as funding agencies participated.

In April 1991, World Wildlife Fund and United States Fish and Wildlife Service received recognition in appreciation for their support of PRMVS. Herbert Raffaele of the United States Fish and Wildlife Service and one of PRMVS's founders and Stephen Cornelius of World Wildlife Fund-US who was the first regional coordinator, received the awards from Christopher Vaughan and Rose Marie Ruiz, President of UNA.

Dr. Mario Lujan, Secretary of the Interior of the United States of America, visited PRMVS and was attended to by Lic. Rose Marie Ruiz, Jorge Fallas, and the United States Ambassador to Costa Rica.

In mid-1991, Dr. James Teer, director of Welder Wildlife Foundation of Sinton, Texas and renowned big-game wildlife management specialist, was assisted by PRMVS in initial logistical planning of the International Wildlife Management Congress, "Integrating People and Wildlife for a Sustainable Future", to be held in San José, Costa Rica on September 19-25, 1993. The Wildlife Society is sponsoring the Congress and PRMVS will be a host institution.

PRMVS was represented in Global Forum-92 in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil from June 1-14, 1992 by professors Claudette Mo and Christopher Vaughan. They managed a booth with posters on seven research projects and general information about PRMVS and BIODOC. During 10 days, Claudette and Chris attended hundreds of interested visitors from all over the world. Many important contacts were made with donor agencies, potential students and professional organizations.

In October 1992, PRMVS was awarded a grant to re-initiate the scientific journal, "Vida Silvestre Neotropical", that had been suspended during its fourth year in 1990 at WWF-US. The journal was and, we hope, will continue to be a major international outlet for Latin American scientists, managers and administrators in the wildlife field. 🐾

*"Human resources are, without a doubt, the single most limiting factor in the movement for sustainable development in the tropics. The solid scientific and managerial training provided by the **Regional Wildlife Management Program for MesoAmerica and the Caribbean** to a generation of natural resource administrators and future policy makers has been an outstanding contribution".*

-Charles Schnell
Resident Director
Organization for Tropical Studies
San José, Costa Rica
(1992)

*"Our evaluation of the Graduate Program of the **Regional Wildlife Management Program for MesoAmerica and the Caribbean** has concluded, and without a doubt, that it is one of the best, if not the best, graduate program in Costa Rica."*

-Independent evaluators of the Council of
University Presidents (CONARE), Costa
Rica. (1992)

GRADUATE TRAINING PROGRAM

PROFESSIONAL STAFF 1990-1991-1992

Christopher Vaughan

Nineteen teaching and research staff have participated in PRMVS since 1990 from six countries, nine at the Ph.D. level and 10 with Master's degrees. Ten were full-time staff in the Program.

Teaching and research staff with UNA positions, courses taught, years in PRMVS, and country of origin

Luisa Castillo	M.S.-Ecotoxicology, Univ. of Metz, France. Thesis Advisor. 1992. <i>Costa Rica</i>
Montserrat Carbonell	Ph.D.-Biological Sciences, Cardiff College-University of Wales, United Kingdom. Vertebrate Population Ecology (field), Thesis Seminar. 1990-1991-1992. <i>Spain</i>
Eduardo Carrillo	M.S.-Wildlife Management, Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica. Introduction to Microcomputers, Vertebrate Population Ecology (field). 1990-1991-1992. <i>Costa Rica</i>
Victor Cartín	Ph.D.-Entomology, University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA. Current Director. 1992. <i>Costa Rica</i>
María Isabel DiMare	Ph.D.-Wildlife Ecology, Texas A&M Univ., USA. Conservation Biology. 1988, 1991. <i>Costa Rica</i>
Jorge Fallas	M.Sc.-Natural Resources, University of Michigan, USA. Habitat Evaluation, Remote Sensing, Geographical Information Systems, Integrated Project. 1988-1989-1990-1991-1992. <i>Costa Rica</i>
Jack Frazier	Ph.D.-Zoology, Oxford University, England. Conservation Biology. 1988-1989-1990. <i>USA</i>
Luko Iilje	Ph.D.-Entomology, Biological Control, University of California, Riverside, USA. Analysis and Control of Vertebrate Pests. 1987-1988-1989-1990-1991-1992. <i>Costa Rica</i>
Horst Korn	Ph.D.-Zoology, University of Malboro, Germany. Population Ecology, Vertebrate Population Ecology (field). 1988-1989-1990-1991-1992. <i>Germany</i>
Michael McCoy	M.Sc.-Wildlife Management, Computer Sciences, Humboldt State University, USA. Introduction to Microcomputers, Basic Statistics, Biometry, Integrated Project, Advanced Statistics, Animal Behavior. 1987-1988-1989-1990-1991-1992. <i>USA</i>
Claudette Mo	D.M.V.-University of Sao Paulo, Brazil. M.S.-Veterinary Science/Wildlife Ecology, University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA. Wildlife Diseases. 1988-1989-1990-1991-1992. <i>Brazil</i>
David Norman	M.A.-Latin American Studies, Tulane University, USA. Wildlife Management Techniques, Wildlife Management. 1987-1988-1989-1990-1991-1992. <i>USA</i>
Jaime Rau	Doctor-Biological Sciences, University of Sevilla, Spain. Integrated Project, Animal Population Ecology. 1991-1992. <i>Chile</i>
Silvia Rodríguez	M.Sc.-Rural Sociology, University of Costa Rica, Costa Rica. Rural Sociology, Integrated Project. 1987-1988-1989-1991-1992. <i>Costa Rica</i>
Raúl Solórzano	M.Sc.-Forestry Economics, University of Costa Rica-CATIE, Costa Rica. Natural Resource Economics Seminar. 1991. <i>Costa Rica</i>

PROFESSIONAL STAFF (Continued)

- Emilio Vargas M.Sc.-Rural Sociology, University of Costa Rica. Rural Sociology, Community Outreach. 1989-1991-1992. *Costa Rica*
- Christopher Vaughan M.Sc.-Wildlands Management, University of Costa Rica-CATIE, Costa Rica. Thesis Seminar, Vertebrate Population Ecology (field), Mammalogy, Conservation Biology, Seminar in Sustainable Development. Current Subdirector. 1987-1988-1989-1990-1991-1992. *USA*
- Sileny Vega Ph.D.-Toxicology, Utah State University, USA. 1990-1991-1992. *Costa Rica*
- Dagmar Werner Ph.D.-Psychology, University of Basel, Switzerland. Wildlife Management, Advanced Wildlife Management. 1989-1990-1991-1992. *Germany*

Guest Professors and Researchers

PRMVS has also received the aid of 14 guest professors and researchers from three countries; eight with Ph.D.'s and six with Master's degrees.

- Marcelo Aranda M.S.-Wildlife Management, Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica. Guest profesor, Vertebrate Population Ecology (field) course. 1992
- Donald Forrester Ph.D.-Zoology, University of California, Davis, USA. Guest lecturer in Wildlife Disease course, 1988, 1990, 1991
- Patrick Herzog M.Sc.-Wildlife Ecology, University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point, USA. Sabbatical from Lethbridge Community College, Canada. Research on scarlet macaw and sea turtle projects. 1991-1992
- Lynn Irby Ph.D.-Wildlife Ecology, Texas A&M University, USA. Fulbright scholar on sabbatical leave from Montana State University. Research on white-tailed deer project. 1990
- Royal Jackson Ph.D.-Recreation, University of New Mexico, USA. Fulbright scholar on sabbatical leave from Oregon State University. Researching ecotourism-recreation. 1992
- Patricia Morton M.Sc.-Zoology, University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA. Taught Environmental Education and Communication course while on leave from Bat Conservation International. 1991
- Lewis Nelson Ph.D.-Wildlife Biology, Colorado State University, USA. On sabbatical leave from University of Idaho, taught Environmental Education and Communication course. 1988-1989-1990
- Wilma Nelson M.S.-Education, University of Idaho, USA. On leave from Idaho Public School System. Taught Environmental Education and Communication course. 1988-1989-1990
- Luis Rodríguez Ph.D.-Veterinary Sciences, University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA. Guest lecturer in Wildlife Disease course. 1988-1990-1991
- Donald Wilson Ph.D.-Zoology, New Mexico State University, USA. Guest researcher on La Selva-Braulio Carrillo Corredor Project. 1988-1989-1990
- Gary Witmer Ph.D.-Wildlife Ecology, Oregon State University, USA. Research on large predators with Christopher Vaughan. 1989-1990-1991-1992
- Grace Wong M.S.-Wildlife Management, Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica. Coordinador of squirrel monkey research/management project. 1990-1991-1992

- Neal Woodman M.Sc.-Paleontology, University of Kansas, USA. Organized PRMVS small mammal museum and worked on mammal inventories. 1990
- Thomas Yuill Ph.D.-Veterinary Sciences and Wildlife Ecology, University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA. Guest lecturer in Wildlife Disease course. 1988-1990-1991

Research Assistants and Special Students

- John Allsteadt B.Sc.-Biology, Lawrence College, USA. Research assistant on caiman project. 1987-1988-1989-1990
- Carlos Calvo B.S.-Biology, Univ. of Costa Rica, Costa Rica. Research assistant on sea turtle project. 1991-1992
- Holly Espach B.Sc.-Biology, Colorado College, USA. Research assistant on white-tailed deer and seed dispersal reforester projects. 1988-1989-1990-1991
- Juliana Lima B.S.-Biology, University of St. Catalina, Brazil. Special student. 1990
- Jill Liske Research assistant on scarlet macaw project. 1990-1991
- Javier Monge M.S.-Wildlife Manage., UNA, Costa Rica. Research assistant on duck control on rice depredate project. 1992
- Mireille Pandolfi D.V.M., France. Special student from Ministry of Rural Development of New Caledonia. 1990
- Joel Sáenz Lic.-Wildlife Management, Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica. Research assistant on seed dispersal reforester project. 1990-1991-1992
- Gina Zanelli D.V.M., Colombia. Research assistant on sea turtle project. 1991

Administrative Staff

- Gloria Arce Lic.-Administration, Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica. Secretary. 1987-1988-1989-1990-1991-1992
- Jorge Barrantes Coordinator of Budget and Equipment. 1987-1988-1989-1991-1992
- Miriam Carranza B.S.-Secretary, Universidad Nacional. Administrative Assistant. 1988-1989-1990
- Hilda Casasola Executive Secretary. 1988-1989-1990-1991-1992
- Emma Peñaranda Secretary. 1989-1990-1991-1992
- Juan Cordero B.S.-Administración, Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica. Administrative Assistant. 1991-1992
- Allan Marín Messenger. 1988-1989-1990-1991-1992
- Enrique Quesada B.S.-Prof. of Education and B.S.-History, University of Costa Rica, Costa Rica. Coordinator of BIODOC. 1988-1989-1990-1991-1992
- Nidia Durán B.S.-Library Sciences, University of Costa Rica, Costa Rica. Document Analyst of BIODOC. 1988-1989-1991-1992

- Lilliana Araya B.S.-Library Sciences, University of Costa Rica, Costa Rica. Librarian of BIODOC. 1990-1991-1992

Gloria's dedicated work, as our first secretary, was essential in the creation of PRMVS.

Jorge Barrantes is a key figure in the efficient control of budget and equipment and maintenance of vehicles.

STUDENT SELECTION AND STATUS

This is a Latin American graduate program given "in situ". It has a very competitive selection process with an average of 60 students applying for 10-13 positions for each promotion. Even after being admitted, students must successfully pass four required undergraduate refresher courses (one 10-week quarter) and an English language competency exam before being admitted to the graduate program. Thus far, 52 Latin Americans from 15 countries have begun graduate training; 25 have graduated, 25 are receiving courses or working on their thesis, and two students left the graduate program after being admitted; one for maternity reasons. One student from the second promotion and two students from the fifth promotion did not approve the refresher courses and thus, did not enter the graduate program. One fifth promotion student passed the refresher courses but left the program to pursue graduate studies in the US.

Eduardo Carrillo

Students of the fifth promotion in Palo Verde National Park during field course in Vertebrate Population Ecology.

Current Status of PRMVS Students

Accepted Students by Country and Promotion						
Country of Origen	Promotion					Total
	I	II	III	IV	V	
Costa Rica	3	3	1	1	2	10
México	2	3	1		1	7
Honduras	2			1		3
Guatemala	2	1				3
Nicaragua			1	1	1	3
El Salvador		1	1	1		3
Panamá		1		2		3
Argentina		1	2		1	4
Venezuela		1	2	1		4
Colombia			2		2	4
Ecuador	1				1	2
Paraguay	1			1		2
Perú				1	1	2
Bolivia		1				1
Uruguay					1	1
Totals	11	12	10	9	10	52

Promotion	Accepted	Separated/Inactive	Active	Graduated
I (1987)	11	0	2	9
II (1988)	12	0	1	11
III (1989)	10	1	4	5
IV (1991)	9	1	8	0
V (1992)	10	0	10	0
Total	52	2	25	25

Christopher Vaughan

Students of second promotion in Caño Negro National Wildlife Refuge during field course in Vertebrate Population Ecology.

MASTER'S DEGREE COURSE CURRICULUM

Course of Study

This is comprised of 27 months divided into three blocks: a) 2.5 months of refresher undergraduate courses; b) 12 months of 10 graduate courses, three seminars, and two field courses; and c) 12 months of thesis work. One week separates each quarter of 10-11 weeks. Emphasis is placed on biodiversity-wildlife management techniques, community outreach-environmental education and communication and working as bio-politicians with local and regional conservation issues. Flexibility is allowed in choosing electives during the third quarter. About 40% of the 27 months is spent in field situations. This curriculum has been adjusted several times, through student and staff feedback, to meet changing skills needed by wildlife biologists in Latin America.

Elective Courses for Advanced Research/Outreach Topics:

Wildlife Management II
 Biological Conservation
 Militarization and Ecology
 in Central America
 Analysis and Control of
 Vertebrate Pests
 Environmental Education
 and Communication
 Multivariate Statistics
 Experimental Designs
 Geographical Information
 Systems
 Pesticides and Wildlife
 Wildlife Diseases
 Topics in Population Eco-
 logy
 Topics in Wildlife Manage-
 ment
 Wildlife Behavior

Refresher Undergraduate

Rural Sociology (3^a)
 Intro. to Microcomputers (3)
 Basic Statistics (3)
 Animal Population Ecology (3)

Quarter 1

Wildlife Management (3)
 Biometry (3)
 Habitat Evaluation (3)
 Wildl. Seminar I (Sustainable
 Development) (1)

Quarter 2

Vertebrate Population Ecology (6)
 Wildl. Manage. Techniques (3)

Quarter 3

Electives I (3)
 Electives II (3)
 Electives III (3)
 Wildlife Seminar II (Vertebrate
 Pest Analysis and Control) (1)

Quarter 4

Thesis Seminar (3)
 Advanced Thesis Topic I (3)
 Community Outreach (3)
 Environmental Education and
 Communication (2)

Quarter 5

Multi-disciplinary Research/
 Outreach Project (6)

Quarter 6

Thesis (14)

Ten week quarter with four introductory undergraduate courses (theory) to bring students up-to-par with basic skills needed to continue with graduate courses.

First quarter of graduate courses (theory). Principles and theory of wildlife management, common statistical tests, experimental designs, habitat evaluation with emphasis in GIS computer-aided uses and principles and theory of sustainable development taught.

Six-week field course in population ecology given in two sites in Costa Rica. Practice in formulation of hypothesis, collection of field data, statistical analysis of data, and presentation (oral and written) of results is stressed. Major techniques used in wildlife management covered in second course during the next weeks.

During third quarter, three electives chosen from a list of offered courses (see side-bar). Independent topics can also be considered. Seminar explores techniques in vertebrate pest analysis and control.

Students write thesis proposals. Seminar teaches proposal writing techniques. Students use one elective to actually write their proposal. Environmental Education and Community Outreach courses concentrate on techniques for communication and working with rural human populations.

A 10-week field course where students choose a topic (research, outreach, management plan, etc.) and carry it through. Involves sampling biota and working with rural communities in sustainable development themes.

Based on original field research of a minimum of eight months with four months of analysis and preparation for defense.

^acredits; Credit Total=60

SELECTED THESIS ABSTRACTS

Biology, Ecology and Utilization of the Lowland Trout (*Agnostomus monticola*) in the Sierra de Manantlán Biosphere Reserve, Jalisco, México

Sonia Navarro Pérez

From November 1989 to September 1990, the lowland trout (*Agnostomus monticola*, Pisces, Mugilidae) was studied in the Sierra de Manantlán, middle-western Mexico. The objective was to collect basic information on the ecology and utilization of this poorly known species, and to develop a management and conservation strategy for the trout population in the Sierra de Manantlán Biosphere Reserve. Trout were found in the three principal watersheds of the Reserve: Ayuquila-Armeria, Purificación and Marabasco, but were rare in the latter two. The study was restricted to the Rio Ayuquila where the species was locally abundant. Information was based on personal observations, net capture and interviews with local fishermen. Trout were present in all sampled habitat types, but most abundant in pools and currents. Capture rate was greater in currents, but largest trout were captured in deep pools. Trout capture rate was greatest during dry season (March to May) when water level was lowest. With onset of rains in June, water level increased and largest individuals migrated downstream to spawn in the river mouth. From there, eggs were probably transported passively to the estuary or ocean; thus, the species can be considered amphidromous. Fishermen of the coastal region reported large numbers of juveniles migrating up river from the estuaries during October and November. Of 509 marked trout, 14 tags were recovered: four were captured in the same site, and two and eight trout moved at least 6 and 10 km upriver, respectively. Based on size distribution, the trout population had three age classes: larvae and juveniles (40-118 mm long), subadults (119-260 mm long) and adults (261 mm or greater). Mature females were larger than males. Adults and subadults were omnivorous, feeding principally on aquatic insects and green algae, with some consumption of terrestrial arthropods, crustaceans, mollusks, nematodes and small fish. The only trout parasite was a leach (*Myzobdella* spp.), found on fins. Recently subsistence fishing became important. Trout, one of the most popular species, is caught with nets principally in the dry season. Fishing pressure during wet season is low, carried out mostly with hook-and-line when trout spawn and migrate to the river mouth. Capture size and size structure differed by locality and showed more harvest in some sites than others. The conservation of trout in the Sierra de Manantlán requires a series of activities, the most important of which include: 1) reduction of river pollution, 2) avoidance of water uses and dams which dry and interrupt the water flow, and 3) organization of community workshops. Organization of fishing cooperatives could reduce fishing pressure in the rivers. Possible regulations should prohibit the use of explosives or poisons, which probably caused the scarcity of fish in the Marabasco watershed. Finally, no fishing should be permitted during the migration and gonad maturation season. ☺

Christopher Vaughan

The Jaguar (*Panthera onca*) in Calakmul Reserve, México: Morphology, Food Habits and Population Density

Jaime Marcelo Aranda Sánchez

The jaguar is the largest American feline and least studied of the world's four large cat species. The present study was done in the Calakmul Biosphere Reserve between May 1989 and May 1990 where the following aspects were analyzed: a) Morphometry: size data and cranial measurement of jaguars of the region; b) Food habits: food spectrum, age and prey size, and seasonal variation in diet; and c) Population density: number of resident and transitory

males, females and young in the study site and speculation about the possible situation of the jaguar in the Calakmul Reserve. Data was obtained from one captive jaguar and from 20 jaguar skulls taken from Calakmul before its creation as a reserve. Weight data was obtained from some of the harvested jaguars. Also 18 jaguar feces and 65 plaster of paris casts of jaguar footprints collected in Calakmul were analyzed. Weight data of *Panthera onca goldmani* found on the Yucatan Peninsula indicated this subspecies as the smallest in Mexico, but possibly not the smallest in America. The collared peccary (*Tayassu tajacu*) was the basic prey item of jaguars in Calakmul, making up 45.8% of identified prey species. Other prey species included the coatimundi (*Nasua nasua*) and brocket deer (*Mazama americana*). In Calakmul, the jaguar largely fed on newborn and young animals. In the study site, I estimated a jaguar density of one per 26-32 km². Sex ratio between males and females was 1:1. ☺

Determination of the Preferred Habitat Characteristics of the Ocellated Turkey (*Agriocharis ocellata*) in Tikal National Park, Guatemala

María José González Fúster

From December 1988 to July 1989, I counted ocellated turkeys (*Agriocharis ocellata*) in different vegetation types in a nucleus area of Tikal National Park, Guatemala. The objective was to determine the preferred seasonal habitat by way of relationships between distinct habitat characteristics and number of turkeys observed. I used 15 trails, between 1.2-2.0 km long, in five different vegetation types: tall forest, low tinto forest, low botan forest, low forest with high understory and secondary forest. I made 163 counts, covering a total of 276.8 km. In two 10 x 20 m plots at random along each trail, I identified tree species with a diameter at breast height (DBH = 1.30 m) greater than 5 cm and measured the following structural variables: DBH and total height; foliage index volume from 0-0.30 m tall, 0.30-1.0 m tall, 1.0-1.5 m tall and 1.5-2.0 m tall; soil cover, litter cover, visibility, and number of trees with a DBH less than 5 cm. Vegetation types could not be separated by trail based on analysis of measured variables. Number of turkeys counted didn't vary significantly between the distinct trails or the eight months of counts. There was also no significant relationship between the vegetative variables measured and the presence of ocellated turkeys. However, a tendency in the observations showed that turkeys preferred tall forest, except during the courting and nesting months (February to June) when males used open areas for their displays and females used pastures or other cleared areas to nest. Apparently, the ocellated turkey selects similar habitat types to that required by *Meleagris gallopavo*, the North American wild turkey. Number of turkeys and flock composition in Tikal village varied throughout the study months. Number of females (adults and juveniles) was significantly lower ($P < 0.05$) between April and July, the period of nesting and caring of young, compared to other months. Composition of turkey groups observed on the road to the city of Flores coincided with the data obtained in village counts. Interviews conducted with hunters throughout El Peten confirmed the results obtained in Tikal concerning turkey habitat selection. The interviews also provided additional information which indicated that the bird can be a generalist concerning habitat selection depending on the conditions of each site. Outside the reproductive season, this species uses the forest, but not necessarily the high forest, if it doesn't exist in the area. In the sabana area, it survives most of the year in the nearby tall forests, and migrates to sabanas during courting and reproductive season. Finally, I suggest that ocellated turkeys be utilized, in El Peten, in accordance with particular biological factors of the species and existing national legislation. ☺

María José González

Composition and Population Size of Caiman (*Caiman crocodilus chiapasius*) and Crocodile (*Crocodylus acutus*) in the Caribbean Coast of Honduras, Central America

Carlos Alberto Cerrato Blanco

A total of 62 surveys of caiman and American crocodile were made between the Trujillo and Rio Patuca zone, on the Caribbean coast of Honduras from January to May 1989; the dry season. Surveys in riverine systems (and distances surveyed included the Rios Aguan (33 km), Capagua (29 km), Sico (19 km), La Criba (6.5 km), Platano (50 km), and Patuca (35 km). The surveys carried out in lake systems included Guaimore (42.5 km), El Lirio (25 km), Bacalar (52 km), Ibans (46.5 km) and Brus (64.5 km). Peripheral areas, including creeks and isolated ponds (34 km) were surveyed. Visible fraction (p) of crocodilians was estimated by 20 counts each in Laguna Bacalar ($p=0.61$) and Rio Sucio ($p=0.60$) to standardize counts for principal water bodies. At least 33% of all crocodiles associated with a body of water were found in nearby peripheral areas. Total population in the study area was estimated based on the visible fraction in principal water bodies and in peripheral areas. This gave a total of 3,109 caimans, of which 1,286 (41%) were found in rivers, 785 (25%) in lakes, and 1,038 (34%) in small peripheral areas. The estimated densities (DE) of caimans in these three habitat types were on average: 7.4 caiman/km of river (range 0.3 to 31.7), equal to 3.7 caiman/km of river shore (range 0.2 to 8.8); and 8 caiman/km of peripheral shore (range 0.9 to 73.6). Greatest number of caiman were found in zones II (Palacios) and I (Brus Laguna). Crocodiles were found very infrequently in the study area. Their numbers varied from 0.5/km of river (range 0 to 2.2) or 0.26/km of river shore, to 0.10/km of lake shore (range 0 to 0.7/km) and 0.5/km of peripheral shore (range 0 to 2.1/km). Largest numbers of crocodiles were found in Rio Aguan. The size structure of the population varied in different water bodies, possibly influenced by recent illegal hunting. There were very few individuals in the D and E categories with LT = 1.5-2.0m and 2.0-2.5m respectively. By interviewing former crocodile hunters, I was able to establish three principal crocodile hunting periods in Honduras, starting in 1930, and the prices paid by local buyers. In general, the crocodile populations are very low, and the caiman populations have reduced ecological densities, due principally to recent hunting. There was no expected correlation between quantifiable habitat components and crocodile densities, due possibly to the effects of recent hunting in the study area. A hunting moratorium for at least three years was recommended for these two species of crocodilians. If it is impossible to avoid the operation of commercial crocodile farms, annual inventories are recommended and experimental quotas should not exceed 10% of the numbers of adults and subadults. If caiman hunting cannot be avoided, it is recommended that only a small proportion of the animals greater than 1.6 m total length be exploited. ☺

Efficiency of Two Methods of Egg Harvesting in Artificial Nests of the Whistling Duck (*Dendrocygna autumnalis*) in Three Habitats of Palo Verde National Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica

José Luis Altuve Marengo

I evaluated the efficiency and effect of egg harvest from whistling duck nestboxes on: laying rate, abandonment and egg predation, clutch size and chick incubation and production, from June to November 1989 in Palo Verde Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica. I placed 44 nest boxes in three habitats (open, intermediate and forested cover) along the marsh edge. Harvest methods were: a) daily, all new eggs except one (Method I); and b) leaving all eggs until sixteenth day after start of incubation, when all but 16 were taken (Method II). Control nestboxes were not harvested. Thirty-three nestboxes (75%) were used by ducks. Insignificantly greatest use was in open habitat. A total of 1,815 eggs were laid. More than one laying female occurred in 76% of nestboxes. Frequency of multiple layings in open habitat was 32% greater than singular ($P < 0.001$). There were more multiple layings than singular with Method I than other methods ($P = 0.006$). There was a positive association between distribution and quantity of rainfall and the number of eggs laid/week ($P < 0.01$). I harvested 792 eggs (44% of those laid) in 22 nests. Number of eggs harvested/nest was insignificantly greater with Method I ($\mu = 40.4$) than Method II ($\mu = 30.7$), nor significant between habitats. Incubated clutches totaled 25. Proportion of incubated nests was 26% and 14% greater with Method I than Method II or Control, respectively, and 30% and 2% greater in open habitat than intermediate and forested habitat, respectively. Incubation success was deficient for nests of Method I-open, Method II-intermediate, and for wooded habitat ($P < 0.005$). A total of 280 chicks (98.6% of hatchlings) abandoned the nestboxes, averaging 20.0 chicks/successful nest without differences between harvest methods. Proportion of hatched fertile eggs was greater in Control (15 eggs, 5.45%) than for Method I (1 egg, 0.64%) or Method II (5 eggs, 4.59%) ($P < 0.01$). Proportion of infertile eggs was greatest in multiple nests of Method II (8 eggs, 7.3%) than in Control (10 eggs, 6%) or Method I (1 egg, 0.64%) ($P < 0.003$). A total of 18 nests were abandoned (37% of total). Insignificantly more nests were abandoned in Control and wooded habitat. During October, 30% of active nests were abandoned ($P < 0.02$). No association existed between rainfall and abandoned nests. Sixteen nests (35%) were destroyed by predators. There were insignificantly more nests destroyed of Method I (57%) than of Method II (38%) than in Control (18%). Nest predation was insignificantly greater in forested habitat (41%) than in intermediate and open habitats (18% and 38%, respectively). During August, predation was 91% of total number of active nests, greater than in the other months ($P < 0.002$). Raccoon (*Procyon lotor*) and boa constrictor (*Boa constrictor*) were the nest predators. Maximal egg harvest with acceptable chick production could be served with nestboxes in open habitat and harvesting by Method I. ☺

Habitat Utilization, Behavior and Diet of the Howler Monkey (*Alouatta palliata*) in a Premontane Moist Forest, Costa Rica

Ronald Sánchez Porras

I determined the number of individuals, social composition, and seasonal variation of: a) monthly (MHR) and total (THIR) home range, b) feeding habits, c) behavior, and d) altitudinal distribution of howler monkeys (*Alouatta palliata*) from September 1989 to March 1990 in two patches of moist, premontane forest: a) 5 ha of altered forest near Rio Jesus, and b) 1000 ha of unaltered forest near Mina Moncada, San Ramón, Alajuela province of Costa Rica. The dry and wet seasons occur from November to April and from May to October, respectively. The troops were observed during 1536 h; a mean 12 h daily during 132 days, with a total of 3067 localizations. Altitudinal distribution was estimated by daily localizations. I observed the phenology of 15 tree species in the diet of monkeys to determine the relation between consumption and availability. I found one troop of 11 howlers in Rio Jesus and four troops of 49 total monkeys in Mina Moncada. MHR in Rio Jesus varied from 1.13 to 3.34 ha, with a THIR of 6.25 ha. In Mina Moncada the MHR varied from 0.003 to 1.95 ha, with a THIR of 2.67 ha. MHR did not vary significantly in Rio Jesus ($P = 0.47$). In Mina Moncada, MHR was greater from February to March than from September to November ($P = 0.05$). MHR was larger in Rio Jesus than in Mina Moncada ($P = 0.01$). Howlers used significantly more numbers of species and of more diversity ($P = 0.07$) in Rio Jesus than in Mina Moncada ($P = 0.003$). In Rio Jesus howlers used 63% of total time in consumption of *Ficus pertusa*, *F. obtusifolia*, *Inga vera* y *F. yaponensis*. In Mina Moncada monkeys used 73% of total time in consumption of *F. obtusifolia*, *F. trachelosyce*, and *F. jimenezii*. In both sites monkeys consumed young leaves more than other food categories ($P = 0.001$). Phenological differences occurred between the 15 tree species observed. Use of a food category was not associated with its availability in most cases. More use with more availability occurred for *F. jimenezii* but not significantly ($r = 0.58, P = 0.13$). More use with less availability occurred with *F. pertusa*, but not significantly ($r = 0.51, P = 0.18$). I observed only six monkey behaviors out of ten priorly established. Monkeys spent most time resting in both sites. Altitudinal distribution varied from 650 to 850 m above sea level in Mina Moncada. Limits are proposed to establish a refuge in Mina Moncada, as well as management recommendations for howlers and their habitat. ☺

Marcelo Aranda

Hunting and Subsistence in Cangandi, a Kuna Indigenous Community, Comarca de San Blas, Panama

Jorge Ventocilla Cuadros

This study was carried out in Cangandi, a community of 279 Kuna inhabitants in the San Blas Comarca, Panama, which consists of a 90% forested 420,000 ha reserve. It is one of only two Kuna Ayala communities of the San Blas Comarca found on continental Panama because the great majority of the 41,000 Kunas live on islands. The objective was to study game hunting in the Kuna culture as a socioeconomic activity. This was carried out by census, interviews and conversations. The first conclusion was that this community lives in a subsistence system, by collecting interrelated resources and performing activities which assure their survival by their own efforts. During 98 days of interviewing, 156 individual hunting trips were carried out, of which 88 were successful. Twenty-nine men from the community participated in hunting activities, but only 5 men were consistent hunters, returning with 75% by weight of the meat harvested. Each of these 5 men had preferred hunting methods and game species. Of the 88 successful hunting expeditions, 115 individuals of 10 species were harvested. Five different hunting methods were identified, and hunting with a rifle and dog was the most common and successful method. Garden hunting (Linares, 1976) or hunting within 7 km of the village where the Kunas had crops planted was the most successful hunting habitat, yielding 75% of the weight of game harvested. This habitat and secondary forest habitat accounted for 90% of the successful hunting expeditions. Garden hunting practices such as that observed by the Kunas of Cangandi have several important ecological and cultural characteristics which promote sustainability: a) type of agriculture practiced and the absence of cattle, b) reduced impact of the dominant economic system outside the Comarca, c) abundant primary forest nearby, d) low human population density, e) persistence of traditional exchange practices and no wildlife commercialization, and f) high fish consumption and high agriculture productivity. 🌿

Marcelo Aranda

Habitat Use and Interactions Between the Vicuña and the Alpaca in the Ulla Ulla National Fauna Reserve, Bolivia.

María Lilián Villalba Murillo

The present study, carried out in the Ulla Ulla National Reserve, Bolivia, from November 1989 to October 1990, focused on obtaining information about habitat preference and use by the vicuña and alpaca, two sympatric species thought to compete with each other. In four study areas, vicuñas and alpacas were censused and data obtained on: habitat type where found, activity realized and group composition. Observations were made on focal pairs (vicuña-alpaca) to measure interspecific interactions. Two principal habitat types were used based on vegetation types. The Humid Prairie habitat consisted of humid areas normally with permanent food and water sources, and dominated by the presence of hydrophilic sedges and juncas. The Pasture habitat was found in drier areas with a predominant of grasses alternating with patches of *Pycnophyllum molle* and *P. stuebelli*, and the xerophytic fern, *Selaginella peruviana*. Analysis of habitat preference indicated that in general, the two camelid species showed a preference for the same habitat type, either Humid Prairie or Pasture. Alpacas used Humid Prairie more frequently and vicuñas used Pasture more frequently. However, during the dry season there was a tendency for both species to utilize Humid Prairie more than Pasture. The pattern of habitat utilization, in daily and seasonal cycles, was similar for both species and observed movements were related to the use of Humid Prairie and water consumption. Correlation analysis showed the vicuña to refuse association with the alpaca, although this tendency lessened when both utilized the Humid Prairie during dry season. No direct interactions were seen between the two species and the presence of dogs and their owners was suspected to be the principal factor which disturbed vicuñas. This suggests an absence of direct competition between the vicuña and the alpaca, but doesn't discard the existence of indirect competition for some food resources. Both species probably show some habitat selection related to prairie area and quality. Finally, although they exhibit similar habitat preferences, the vicuña can take advantage of marginal habitats better than the alpaca, although it needs access to a permanent water source. 🌿

Distribution, Ecology and Present Status of Psittacids in Concepción Department, Paraguay

Nancy Esther López Huerta

This study was carried out from October 11, 1988 to October 29, 1989 in Concepción (23°00'S and 57°00'W), a state in Paraguay. I utilized 10 localities and 1932 censusing stations (1075 inside vegetation and 857 on vegetation borders). The number of individuals between communities (inside vs. border) varied seasonally in xerophytic vegetation of Primavera and San Pablo ($H=7.146$, $d.f.=3$, $P<0.05$) and the "cerrado" of Centurion and San Luis de la Sierra ($H=12.321$, $d.f.=3$, $P<0.05$). Relative abundance indexes indicated a low population density for *Anodorhynchus hyacinthinus*, *Ara maracana*, *Ara auricollis*, *Ara chloroptera*, *Amazona vinacea* and *Forpus xanthopeterygis*. At the "cerrado" of Centurion and San Luis de la Sierra there were 11 and six species, respectively, of psittacids between June and September of 1989. *Anodorhynchus hyacinthinus* was present only in the "cerrado" of the northcentral part of Concepción. *Ara maracana* and *Ara auricollis* were restricted to the extreme northwest in xerophytic vegetation. Based on 1968 and 1988 vegetation maps, major causes of vegetation alteration in the last 20 yrs were agriculture, cattle, forestry exploitation, limestone mining, human settlements and road opening. In 1988, cover was 19.33% for the "cerrado", 22.41% for the xerophytic and 7.52% for the deciduous and mesophytic associations. The 16 species of psittacids fed on mesocarp, endocarp, cotyledon, nectar and flowers of 59 plant species, both in the canopy and understory. Distribution of flowering and fruiting peaks varied with association. In the case of the Centurion "cerrado", neither flowering ($X^2=12.0$, $d.f.=5$, $P<0.05$), nor fruiting ($X^2=18.3$, $d.f.=5$, $P<0.05$) was uniform. *Acrocomia totai* had the greatest number of flowering individuals. The reproductive period for psittacids lasted from 3 to 7 mo, depending on the species. *Acrocomia totai* had a high density of dry, old trees with snags in the cerrado used by psittacids. There were many termite nests available for psittacids in Santa Sofía, Centurion and San Luis de la Sierra ($X^2=11.190$, $d.f.=5$, $P<0.05$). The "cerrado" of the northcentral area of the serranía of San Luis de la Sierra was a potential nesting site of eight species of psittacids. A fire in August, 1988 caused the loss of 1450 ha of "cerrado" and the death of three (1.05%) young *Ara chloroptera*. In Fonciere, an annual loss of 0.20 nests/ha was caused by commercial purposes. In 1989 storms affected the nesting sites of *Ara chloroptera*. The rural human population exploited eight species of psittacid chicks, juveniles, and adults. In Concepción, 16 species of psittacids were subject to local commercialization, with *Anodorhynchus hyacinthinus* being the most highly prized (US\$300 each). In Fonciere, which is a private farm, I recommend a psittacid conservation program be initiated. It is important to control trapping and nest site destruction under a national system of control of species commercialization. ☺

Alteration of a Yungas Forest in Tucuman, Argentina, and the Use of Birds as Ecological Indicators for the Design of Buffer Zones in Protected Areas

Roberto Vides Almonacid

I evaluated the changes in avifaunal community structure as a consequence of Yungas forest alteration, in the Sierra de San Javier, approximately 26°47'S-65°22'W, Tucuman, Argentina. I then elaborated guidelines for buffer zone design in a protected area, using birds as ecological indicators. I considered nine habitat types in the design: a) cultivated land (sugarcane, citrus trees) and forestry plantations with non-native pine species, b) secondary, both non-forested (pasture-brush) and forested (young, mature and chaparral-secondary forest) and c) recently altered primary forest. In each habitat, I established five sampling points. Each point was visited six times in the summer (February-April) and six times in the winter (June-August) of 1991. For analysis of total bird species richness, bird species richness distributed in Yungas and the individual abundance, I grouped the data from the sample for each sample point. For species composition, I grouped all the sample points by habitat. In each sample point, I evaluated the habitat structure, considering thirteen vegetation variables. For analysis of the relationships birds/habitat, I considered each sample point independently. Results indicated marked changes in species richness, abundance and composition between habitats. I registered greater species richness and abundance, particularly of Yungas species, in naturally forested habitats (both secondary and altered primary) and less species richness, abundance and dominance not linked to Yungas forests in the non-forested habitats (sugarcane and secondary pasture-brush) or cultivated trees (citrus and pine plantations). During winter, secondary forests were important for maintenance of bird populations of Yungas forest. Of the habitat variables considered, shrub cover of 1-10 m, tree species diversity and basal area showed highly significant correlations ($P<0.0001$) with the majority of the bird variables. I made gradients with the averages per contacts per habitat for the 16 most abundant bird species, according to the increasingly complex different habitat types. With the resulting information, I established preliminary criteria for individual bird species or group selection, as ecological indicators of degree of alteration of the Yungas forest in the study area. From this, I suggest the most adequate habitats as buffer zones for the protected area and those land-use practices which "buffer" the protected area from human pressure. The altered primary forest used for extractive firewood use could protect most of the biota, while annual monoculture in large areas and without arboreal vegetative corridors for the wildlife would be the least adequate option. However, alternative practices in the protected interphase area/intensive use area could be plantation forestry and secondary forests with sustainable silvicultural management (wood and firewood) which consists of mixed forests with native forestry species. ☺

LICENCIATURE AND MASTERS THESES COMPLETED: 1988-1992

LICENCIATURE (LIC.)

Carrillo, Eduardo. 1988. (Costa Rican). Tourist influence on raccoon behavior patterns in Manuel Antonio National Park, Costa Rica. 70 pp. Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.

Monge, Javier. 1990. (Costa Rican). Reproductive cycle and diet of the variegated squirrel (Sciuridae, Rodentia) in the Nicoyan Peninsula, Costa Rica. 81 pp. Luko Hilje, Major Advisor.

Rodríguez, Miguel. 1989. (Costa Rican). Size and composition of the social groups of the white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) on San Lucas Island, Costa Rica. 62 pp. Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.

Sáenz, Joel. 1990. (Peruvian). Ecology of two groups of white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) liberated into a new habitat. 135 pp. Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.

Wong, Grace. 1990. (Costa Rican). Ecology of the squirrel monkey (*Saimiri oerstedii citrinellus*) in Manuel Antonio National Park, Costa Rica. 57 pp. Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.

MASTERS (M.S.)

Alfaro, Juan. 1993. (Costa Rican, I Promotion). I. Efficacy of methods to control the Mexican grackle (*Quiscalus mexicanus*) in urban roosts of Costa Rica. II. An empirical method to estimate minimum sample size for morphological measurements of the Mexican grackle (*Quiscalus mexicanus*) in Costa Rica. 85 pp. Michael McCoy, Major Advisor.

Altuve, José. 1992. (Venezuelan, II Promotion). Efficiency of two methods of egg harvesting in artificial nests of the whistling duck (*Dendrocygna autumnalis*) in three habitats of Palo Verde National Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica. 70 pp. Michael McCoy, Major Advisor.

Aranda, Marcelo. 1990. (Mexican, II Promotion). The jaguar (*Panthera onca*) in Calakmul Reserve, México; morphology, food habits and population density. 93 pp. Jorge Fallas, Major Advisor.

Bonino, Never. 1990. (Argentinian, II Promotion). Natural history, damage evaluation and control of the pocket gopher *Orthogeomys heterodus* (Rodentia, Geomyidae) in an agricultural zone of Costa Rica. 105 pp. Luko Hilje, Major Advisor.

Calvopiña, José. 1990. (Ecuadorian, I Promotion). Reintroduction of the white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) to Cobano, Puntarenas, Costa Rica. 73 pp. Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.

A total of 25 Master's degrees have been completed by the 33 students of the first three promotions. Two additional theses have been successfully defended, and by mid-1993 the other five students should finish.

Carrillo, Eduardo. 1990. (Costa Rican, II Promotion). Ecology of the crab-eating raccoon (*Procyon cancrivorus*) in Manuel Antonio National Park, Costa Rica. 105 pp. Horst Korn, Major Advisor.

Cerrato, Carlos. 1992. (Honduran, I Promotion). Composition and population size of caiman (*Caiman crocodilus chiapasius*) and crocodile (*Crocodylus acutus*) in the Caribbean coast of Honduras, Central America. 184 pp. David Norman, Major Advisor.

Chalukian, Silvia. 1991. (Argentinian, III Promotion). Regeneration, succession and plant invaders in a Yungas forest, Salta, Argentina. 180 pp. Horst Korn, Major Advisor.

Cuarón, Alfredo. 1991. (Mexican, II Promotion). Conservation of primates and their habitats in southern México. 113 pp. Horst Korn, Major Advisor.

González, María José. 1992. (Guatemalan, I Promotion). Determination of the preferred habitat characteristics of the ocellated turkey (*Agriocharis ocellata*) in Tikal National Park, Guatemala. 183 pp. David Norman, Major Advisor.

Hartasánchez, Ilia. 1992. (Mexican, I Promotion). Ecological aspects of the wetlands of Laguna Términos with emphasis in species of ciconiiforms in the Usumacinta Delta, Grijalva, México. David Norman, Major Advisor.

Hernández, Daniel. 1991. (Costa Rican, I Promotion). I. Aquatic flora and its annual changes in a seasonal Costa Rican marsh. II. Habitat use by ducks (Anatidae) in a seasonal Costa Rican marsh. 105 pp. Michael McCoy, Major Advisor.

Lara, Oscar. 1990. (Guatemalan, II Promotion). Estimation of the size and structure of a population of *Crocodylus moreletii* Dumeril and Dumeril (Crocodylidae, Reptilia) in the lakes of Petén Itzá, Sal-Petén, Petenchel, and Yaxha, El Peten, Guatemala. 67 pp. Dagmar Werner, Major Advisor.

López, Nancy. 1993. (Paraguayan, I Promotion). Distribution, ecology and present status of Psittacids in Concepción Department, Paraguay. 337 pp. Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.

Malavassi, Leda. 1991. (Costa Rican, I Promotion). I. Grison (*Gallictis vittata*) capture. II. Grison (*Gallictis vittata*) activity in captivity. III. A possible reproductive cycle for the Grison (*Gallictis vittata*) in Costa Rica. 99 pp. Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.

March, Ignacio. 1991. (Mexican, I Promotion). Habitat evaluation and present status of the white-lipped peccary (*Tayassu pecari*) in México. 235 pp. Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.

Márquez, César. 1992. (Colombian, III Promotion). Composition of the diurnal raptor community of Palo Verde National Park, Costa Rica. 135 pp. Horst Korn, Major Advisor.

Monge, Javier. 1992. (Costa Rican, III Promotion). Population characteristics and habitat use of the cotton rat (*Sigmodon hispidus*) in Cañas, Guanacaste, Costa Rica. 92 pp. Luko Hilje, Major Advisor.

Navarro, Sonia. 1992. (Mexican, II Promotion). Biology, ecology and utilization of the lowland trout (*Agnostomus monticola*) in the Sierra de Manantlán Biosphere Reserve, Jalisco, México. 84 pp. Horst Korn, Major Advisor.

Sánchez, Ronald. 1990. (Costa Rican, II Promotion). Habitat utilization, behavior, and diet of the howler monkey (*Alouatta palliata*) in a premontane moist forest, Costa Rica. 109 pp. Michael McCoy, Major Advisor.

Velazco, Eduardo. (Colombian, III Promotion). Distribution and utilization of the paramo fauna in the Valle and Cauca Departments of Colombia. Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.

Ventocilla, Jorge. 1990. (Panamanian, II Promotion). Hunting and subsistence in Cangandj; a Kuna indigenous community, Comarca de San Blas, Panama. 190 pp. Emilio Vargas, Major Advisor.

Vides, Roberto. 1991. (Argentinian, III Promotion). Alteration of a Yungas forest in Tucuman, Argentina and the use of birds as ecological indicators for the design of buffer zones in protected areas. 210 pp. Horst Korn, Major Advisor.

Villaba, Lilián. 1991. (Bolivian, II Promotion). Habitat use and interactions between the vicuña and the alpaca in the Ulla Ulla National Fauna Reserve, Bolivia. 128 pp. Horst Korn, Major Advisor.

Wong, Grace. 1991. (Costa Rican, II Promotion). Habitat use, and population composition and density of the squirrel monkey (*Saimiri oerstedii citrinellus*) in the Manuel Antonio National Park zone, Quepos, Costa Rica. 78 pp. Horst Korn, Major Advisor.

THESES IN PROGRESS

I Promotion (Initiated thesis June 1988)

Cabrera, Milton. (Guatemalan). Influence of vegetation on the abundance of some large vertebrates in three new protected areas of the Peten, Guatemala. **Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.**

Midence, Sergio. (Honduran). Distribution and present status of the Cracid family in Honduras. **David Norman, Major Advisor.**

II Promotion (Initiated thesis June 1989)

Sermeño, Alfonso. (Salvadoran). Estimation of the density and habitat use of the great curassow (*Crax rubra*, Cracidae) in the El Imposible National Park, El Salvador. **Dagmar Werner, Major Advisor.**

III Promotion (Initiated thesis March 1991)

Deza, María. (Venezuelan). Abundance and population structure of the galapago (*Podocnemis yogli*, Pelomedusidae) in the Hacienda Masaguaral, Guarico State, Venezuela and their cultural importance for local inhabitants. **David Norman, Major Advisor. (*)**

Guido, Maritza. (Salvadoran). Characterization of damage by parakeets and parrots (Aves: Psittacidae) in corn crops (*Zea mays* L.) and evaluation of control methods, Cóbano, Puntarenas. **Luko Hilje, Major Advisor. (*)**

Rodríguez, Manuel. (Venezuelan). Evaluation of the frugivore bird population of Henri Pittier National Park, Venezuela. **David Norman, Major Advisor.**

Ruiz, Gustavo. (Nicaraguan). Reproductive response of the slider turtle (*Trachemys scripta*) to natural habitat management in San Sebastian Lake, Caño Negro, Costa Rica. **David Norman, Major Advisor.**

IV Promotion (Initiated thesis May 1992)

Araúz, Jacobo. (Panamanian). Conservation status of the squirrel monkey (*Saimiri oerstedii citrinellus*) in its original distribution area. **Eduardo Carrillo, Major Advisor.**

Araúz, Marta. (Panamanian). Incubation rates of the Ridley sea turtle (*Lepidochelys olivacea*) in Playa Ostional, Ostional National Wildlife Refuge, Guanacaste, Costa Rica. **Claudette Mo, Major Advisor.**

Morera, Rodrigo. (Costa Rican). Importance of key-stone plant species for populations of the white-faced monkey (*Cebus capucinus*) and the howler monkey (*Alouatta palliata*) in a tropical dry forest of Costa Rica. **Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.**

Marineros, Leonel. (Honduran). Management plan for the scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*) in Carara Biological Reserve and adjoining areas, Costa Rica. **Christopher Vaughan, Major Advisor.**

Paz, Oscar. (Salvadoran). Effects on the aquatic avifauna of the use of organophosphate pesticides in inundated ricefields of the Tempisque watershed, Guanacaste, Costa Rica. **Luisa Castillo, Major Advisor.**

Salcedo, Carlos. (Peruvian). Hormonal evaluation of the reproductive cycle of birds of the genus *Ara* in captivity. **Claudette Mo, Major Advisor.**

Torrealba, Isa. (Venezuelan). Eco-ethological aspects of the collared peccary (*Tayassu tajacu*) and its relationship with neighboring human communities in a tropical rain forest, Costa Rica. **Jaime Rau, Major Advisor.**

V Promotion These students started coursework in May 1992. Will initiate thesis in August 1993.

Javier Beltrán (Argentina)
Federico Chinchilla (Costa Rica)
Eduardo Naranjo (Mexico)
Cecilia Pacheco (Ecuador)
María del Pilar Rivas (Colombia)
Joel Sáenz (Peru)
Pedro Sánchez (Colombia)
Wilfredo Segura (Costa Rica)
Romeo Spinolla (Uruguay)
Teresa Zúñiga (Nicaragua)

(*) Denotes thesis defended successfully, and graduation pending final thesis draft corrections.

"University programs in Conservation Biology have three critical, interconnected components: Teaching, Research, and Outreach. *The Regional Wildlife Management Program for MesoAmerica and the Caribbean* is no exception, and the many ongoing research and outreach projects by staff members and current and former students are testimony to a successful program. A successful project will provide training to students, solutions to problems, and information to users. Costa Rica in particular and Latin America in general are well-served by this program."

-Don Wilson, Ph.D.
Director, Biodiversity Programs and
President of the Association for
Tropical Biology
National Museum of Natural History
Smithsonian Institution
Washington, D.C.
(1993)

STAFF RESEARCH, MONITORING, MANAGEMENT, AND OUTREACH

STAFF PROJECTS

Research, monitoring, management, and outreach aimed at providing alternative natural resource uses necessary to achieve "sustainable development".

Restoration of a seasonal tropical freshwater marsh, Palo Verde National Park, Costa Rica. The elimination of cattle grazing from this marsh in 1980 stimulated a massive cattail (*Typha dominguensis*) invasion that caused a dramatic decline in waterfowl usage. Since 1987, research determined the most efficient method to eliminate cattail from the 500 ha marsh and re-establish the earlier habitat on this most important wetland in Central America, and home to over 60 migratory bird species, including 60,000 whistling ducks and blue-winged teal in 1979. The use of agricultural machinery to eliminate cattail (in 70 ha) and the use of cattle grazing by local ranchers to maintain the preferred vegetation mix has increased duck numbers back to 33,000 in 1991, up from a low of 3500 in 1988. This sustainable development project has received funds from the Organization of American States, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, the World Wildlife Fund, Douroucoul Foundation, Project Lighthawk, Organization for Tropical Studies, Costa Rican Wildlife Service, Audubon Society (Fairfax, Va. Chapter) and PRMVS. **Michael McCoy** (coordinator), **Daniel Hernández** (co-researcher).

Ecological studies of the brown caiman (*Caiman crocodilus fuscus*) in Caño Negro National Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica.

The objective of this research project was to compile ecological information (population status and dynamics, recruitment, food habits, nesting, habitat utilization, seasonal movements) and threats to the brown caiman and then manage this species in Caño Negro Wildlife Refuge. Research was conducted from 1986 to 1990 and was funded by the Organization of American States and PRMVS. **Christopher Vaughan** (coordinator) and **John Allsteadt** (co-researcher).

Christopher Vaughan

White-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) management in Costa Rica. The white-tailed deer is one of the most important big game animals in Latin America and also has cultural, ecological, psychological, and social importance for humans. Unfortunately it has been heavily overexploited and populations are very small. This study describes the life cycle and ecological requirements of white-tailed deer in the tropical dry forest. It also works with environmental education and extension in rural communities. The overall goal is to restore white-tailed deer populations throughout Costa Rica to levels which can provide protein to rural people, recreational sport for hunters, aesthetic values to the general public, a food source for large predators, and also play a biological role as seed dispersers. A total of two licenciature and three master's degree theses were carried out on white-tailed deer biology and management in connection with the project. This project is funded by World Wildlife Fund-US, Organization of American States, Costa Rican Wildlife Service, and PRMVS. **Christopher Vaughan** (coordinator), **Sergio Brenes**, **José Calvopiña**, **María Isabel DiMare**, **Holly Espach**, **Miguel Rodríguez**, **Joel Saéñz**, **Vivienne Solís** and **Lynn Irby** (co-researchers).

Christopher Vaughan

Green iguana (*Iguana iguana*) management in Mesoamerica.

The research on iguana management aims at developing the scientific and technical basis for conserving and increasing iguana numbers in order to provide protein and income from iguana meat and eggs for campesinos. Management schemes examined include raising iguanas to harvestable size in confined conditions, management of wild populations, or combinations of captive rearing and management in wild areas. Management of free-living iguana populations requires tropical forest, the natural habitat of the species. One of the objectives of this project is to investigate whether reforestation with native multiple-purpose trees for iguana management might be a viable means to provide campesinos with needed tree projects (timber, fuel wood, fruits), in addition to providing a medium for producing animal protein. The research also explores possibilities of maximizing the overall productivity of small farming systems. This project is funded by W. Alton Jones Foundation, James Smithsonian Society, InterAmerican Foundation, NORAD (Norway) and PRMVS. **Dagmar Werner** (coordinator).

Dagmar Werner

Whistling duck egg production in artificial nest structures. This research project began in 1986 with experiments on the efficiency and success of whistling duck reproduction in wood boxes in the marsh at Palo Verde National Park. The objective was to increase the number of nesting ducks in Palo Verde due to a supposed scarcity of natural nesting cavities and to provide an alternative food source for local campesinos. The nesting population increased from 10 to 100 pairs in five years. In 1989 over 1800 eggs were laid in 44 boxes with 792 eggs harvested and 280 chicks fledged. Daily harvest of eggs from boxes stimulated more eggs laid, smaller clutches, less abandonment and more successful hatching than no harvest at all. This project is funded by the Douroucouli Foundation, Costa Rican Wildlife Service, Organization of American States and PRMVS. Michael McCoy (coordinator), Juan Rodríguez (Costa Rican Wildlife Service), José Luis Altuve. (co-researchers).

Michael McCoy

Evaluation and reduction of rice loss from ducks in Guanacaste, Costa Rica. Rice farmers can lose up to 50% or more of their planted seed to duck predation at night. In early 1992 the coordinator began research on reducing this damage, especially during the planting and early growing season in a 600 ha project of small-scale farmers adjacent to Palo Verde National Park. He is testing a mechanical method (propane detonators) and has been able to virtually eliminate damage completely with this method, thus providing a solution acceptable to farmers without harming the large duck population. This project is funded by CONICIT (Costa Rican National Science Foundation) and PRMVS. Michael McCoy (coordinator), Javier Monge (co-researcher).

Michael McCoy

Research aimed at providing stable resources for local communities to permanently benefit from ecotourism.

Conservation of the squirrel monkey (*Saimiri oerstedii citrinellus*) in Costa Rica. The squirrel monkey is the smallest and least widespread of the four known Costa Rican wild primates. As a continuation of the thesis work begun in 1987 by Grace Wong, this project is concerned with developing a four stage long-term conservation strategy to assure survival of the species in the Manuel Antonio National Park region: a) elaborate an environ-

mental education program, b) continue to collect information on the ecology of the species, c) establish the actual distribution and forest patch sizes of the subspecies throughout its range, and d) protect habitat and actively manage the habitat and population. This project is funded by Conservation International, the Phoenix Zoo and the Organization of American States. Grace Wong and Eduardo Carrillo (coordinators).

Tom Damon

Ecology and conservation of the scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*) in Carara Biological Reserve, Costa Rica. In early 1990, studies began on the scarlet macaw population through monthly counts, food habit studies, nesting counts, and interviews with tourists and local inhabitants in the Carara region. Preliminary results showed a monthly range from 80 (February) to 217 (June) scarlet macaws, a 7% recruitment rate, a nesting season from December to June and diet consisting of fruits of 15 tree species. Over 32,000 foreign visitors will have attempted to observe the scarlet macaw in Carara in 1992. In total they will have spent about \$4,000,000 in Costa Rica between hotels, meals, tour guides and/or rental cars. Thus, a scarlet macaw in Carara is worth about \$20,000 alive. A management plan will be completed by a PRMVS graduate student and the coordinator in mid-1993. This project is funded by the Organization of American States and PRMVS. Christopher Vaughan (coordinator), Pat Herzog, Jill Liske, Leonel Marineros (co-researchers).

Tom Damon

Reproductive biology of the boat-billed heron in the Tempisque River, Costa Rica: Possible impact of tourism. The boat-billed heron is considered an indicator species for aquatic ecosystems because of its high position in the food chain, and its susceptibility to contaminants and human disturbance. Numbers of boat-billed herons and other storks have diminished recently and some nesting colonies have disappeared in the lower watershed of the Tempisque river. The number of tourists visiting the area has increased dramatically during the last 5 years. Agrochemical use has also increased in the region. The principle objective is to analyze various factors that influence nesting of boat-bills and to observe reproductive success of distinct colonies with and without tourist disturbance in the river. It is hoped that the results will aid park administrators with tourist control and management. Montserrat Carbonell (coordinator), Daniel Hernández (co-researcher).

Specific research on wildlife ecology aimed at conservation and/or restoration of habitats or wildlife populations.

Olive Ridley Sea turtle Conservation in Costa Rica. This long-term monitoring and ecological research project was begun in 1982 by biologist Stephen Cornelius, and continued by the coordinator. It consists in monitoring nesting of the ridley sea turtle at Nancite Beach in Guanacaste National Park, Costa Rica and determining those factors which affect nesting success. For four years, work has focused on bacteria and fungi as turtle egg predators, which account for up to 50% of the nesting loss in Nancite Beach. This project is funded by World Wildlife Fund-US, the Earth Island Foundation and PRMVS. Claudette Mo (coordinator), Marta Arauz, Rodrigo Morera, Gina Zintelli, Carlos Calvo (co-researchers).

Christopher Vaughan

Role of vertebrate seed dispersers in the restoration of the tropical dry forest, Costa Rica. The objective is to conserve or restore the biological diversity of the tropical dry forest through understanding the role that seed dispersers play in the regeneration dynamics of the system. Since 1990, we have studied the home range, habitat utilization, diet and behavior of the coatimundi (*Nasua narica*) in three different habitats (cloud forest, plateau forest and beach forest) in Guanacaste National Park, using radiotelemetry, scat collection and direct observation. We have also studied the white-faced monkey (*Cebus capucinus*), howler monkey (*Alouatta palliata*), and white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*). More mammal and bird species will be studied in the future. This project is funded by the Organization of American States and PRMVS. Christopher Vaughan (coordinator), Joel Sáenz, Holly Espach and Rodrigo Morera (co-researchers).

Joel Sáenz

Evaluation of biological resource diversity of Costa Rica using remote sensing and geographical information systems. This 2-year project, in collaboration with the Archbold Tropical Research Center, Clemson University, and financed by US-AID will evaluate available data sources and establish data requirements for the international application of gap analysis. A second task is the development of a GIS framework for the spatial prioritization of both conservation and sustainable development land areas. Gap analysis uses GIS to overlay species distribu-

tions with ecosystem boundaries and with the boundaries of protected areas, thus, identifying efficient linkages in the conservation network. Jorge Fallas (coordinator), Christopher Vaughan (co-researcher).

Evaluation of band S radar with HH and VV polarization in tropical environments. This research project is aided by both the European and the Canadian Space Agencies. The objective is to determine the behavior of radar spectral signatures under forested and agricultural conditions in and around Palo Verde National Park. Jorge Fallas (coordinator).

Policies of wildlands administration.

Role of the Costa Rican state in the conservation of protected areas. This study concerns the role which the Costa Rican government plays in wildland protection. The two specific subjects being analyzed are: a) the abandonment of governmental functions in relation to the management or conservation of the biodiversity of the protected wildlands, and b) the contradictory politics between conservation and development of the Costa Rican government in the protection of wildland areas and their areas of influence. This project is the doctorate thesis of the coordinator in the Land Tenure Center, University of Wisconsin-Madison and is funded by the Organization of American States and PRMVS. Silvia Rodríguez (coordinator).

Marcelo Avendaño

Impact of agricultural chemicals on wildlife.

Evaluation of the effects of pesticides on wildlife in Costa Rica. This research aims at evaluating the toxic effect that pesticides have on birds and other wildlife groups, with emphasis in the anticholinester pesticides. After calibrating equipment and optimizing enzymatic action measuring methods, dead animals suspected to have been poisoned by pesticides will be analyzed. Research began in 1990 and is funded by the Organization of American States and PRMVS. Sileny Vega (coordinator).

Public outreach and education about reptiles in South America.

Elaboration of the book, "Amphibians and reptiles of Paraguay". This book will include 320 pages of text and 68 color photographs of 26 amphibians and 37 reptiles characteristic of the Paraguayan Chaco. It is both a field guide and an important natural history guide with an extensive bibliography. Research began in 1987 and is funded by the Homeland Foundation, CA and PRMVS. David Norman (author). ☺

PRESENTATIONS AT PROFESSIONAL MEETINGS 1987-1992

- Vaughan, C. 1987. Graduate training in wildlife biology at an international level. I International Symposium on Latin American Mammalogy. Cancún, México. Jun. 1987. *
- Vaughan, C. 1987. Coyote range expansion in Costa Rica and Panama. I International Symposium on Latin American Mammalogy. Cancún, México. Jun. 1987. *
- Carrillo, E. 1988. Influence of human presence on raccoon behavior in Costa Rica. Organization for Tropical Studies Silver Anniversary Symposium. University of Florida, Gainesville, Florida. **
- McCoy, M. 1988. Status of the family cracidae in Costa Rica. Second International Symposium on the Family Cracidae. Caracas, Venezuela. Mar. 3-5, 1988.
- Vaughan, C. 1988. The Regional Wildlife Management Program as an example of international cooperation. II International Wildlife Congress. Acapulco, México. May 17-20, 1988. *
- Our staff and students gave a total of 72 papers at international meetings and 10 papers at national events, based on original research. Ten professors and 11 students participated.***
- Werner, D. 1988. Benefits of iguana management in Latin America. II International Wildlife Congress. Acapulco, México. May 17-20, 1988. *
- Mo, C. 1988. The study of wildlife disease in Latin America. XI Panamerican Congress of Veterinary Sciences. Lima, Perú. Aug. 14-20, 1988. *
- Mo, C. 1988. Are fungi and bacteria to blame for the loss of marine turtle eggs (*Lepidochelys olivacea*)? XI Panamerican Congress of Veterinary Sciences. Lima, Perú. Aug. 14-20, 1988. *
- Vaughan, C. 1988. White-tailed deer management in Costa Rica. I Central American Biology Congress. Guatemala, Guatemala. Nov. 28-Dec. 2, 1988.
- Vaughan, C. 1988. The importance of biodiversity conservation in Costa Rica. I Central American Biology Congress. Guatemala, Guatemala. Nov. 28-Dec. 2, 1988.
- Mo, C. 1989. Veterinary medicine and wildlife. II National Congress of Veterinary Medicine. La Ceiba, Honduras. Nov. 25-26, 1989.
- Mo, C. 1989. Bluetongue in Central America. II National Congress of Veterinary Medicine. La Ceiba, Honduras. Nov. 25-26, 1989.
- Fallas, J. and C. Valverde. 1989. Potential site selection for reforestation with cypress (*Cupressus lusitanica* Mill) using a geographical information system of low cost. I cartographic model. II Latinamerican Conference on Technology of Geographic Information Systems (GIS). Mérida, Venezuela.
- Korn, H. 1989. Small mammals and the cyclic mosaic theory of ecosystems. Germany. Sept. 6-9, 1989.
- Werner, D. 1989. Management of green iguanas in captivity and in wildland areas. I World Herpetology Congress. Canterbury, England. Sept. 11-20, 1989. *
- March, I. 1989. The Lacandon rainforest of Chiapas. National Audubon Society. Biennial Convention. Plenary Session. Tucson, Arizona. Sept. 14, 1989.
- March, I. 1989. Lacandon ecology. The Lacandon Rainforest Project Conference. Seattle, Washington. Sept. 23, 1989.
- Fallas, J. 1989. Geographic information systems: a new technology for natural resource planning. III National Hydrological Resource Congress. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 1989. *
- Fallas, J. and C. Valverde. 1989. Rainfall erosion in May from the Juan Santamaria Pluviological Station, Alajuela, Costa Rica. III National Hydrological Resource Congress. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 1989. *
- Salas, I. and C. Mo. 1989. Experimental infection of Olive Ridley (*Lepidochelys olivacea*) turtle eggs with fungus and bacteria. Microbiology Congress. San José, Costa Rica. Dec. 14-16, 1989. *
- Frazier, J. 1990. Marine turtles in Chile. X Workshop on Conservation and Biology of Marine Turtles. Hilton Head Island, South Carolina. Feb. 20-24, 1990. *
- Mo, C. 1990. Are fungi and bacteria responsible for olive ridley egg loss? X Workshop on Conservation and Biology of Marine Turtles. Hilton Head Island, South Carolina. Feb. 20-24, 1990. **
- Mo, C. 1990. Olive ridley sea turtle population dynamics in Nancite Beach, Costa Rica. X Workshop on Conservation and Biology of Marine Turtles. Hilton Head Island, South Carolina. Feb. 20-24, 1990. **

*abstract presented; **poster and abstract presented

Frazier, J. 1990. Closing remarks. III Regional Workshop on Marine Turtles in the Yucatán Peninsula, México. Mar. 6-8, 1990.

Frazier, J. 1990. International resource conservation: where's the challenge? 55th North American Wildlife and Natural Resources Conference. Denver, Colorado. Mar. 20, 1990. **

Vaughan, C. 1990. Patterns in natural resource destruction and conservation in Central America: a case for optimism? 55th North American Wildlife and Natural Resources Conference. Denver, Colorado. Mar. 20, 1990. **

Papers were presented in 12 Latin American countries, nine states of the USA, two countries in Europe, and in Canada and Japan.

Fallas, J. 1990. "Map-for-the-PC": a geographical information system for IBM and compatible microcomputers. III Venezuelan Geography Congress. Mérida, Venezuela. Mar. 19-23, 1990. *

Frazier, J. 1990. Ecological economics of marine turtles: challenges in sustainable exploitation of a resource which is both local and international. Symposium of Ecological Economics of Sustainability. Washington, D.C. May 21-23, 1990. *

Werner, D. 1990. Green iguana management. II International Symposium on Wildlife Management. Edmonton, Alberta, Canada. Jun. 3-9, 1990. *

Vaughan, C. 1990. The Regional Wildlife Management Program for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean: training center for Latin America "in situ". First Joint Meeting American Society of Mammalogist and Argentinean Society of Mammalogists. Buenos Aires, Argentina. Jun. 17-20, 1990. *

Vaughan, C. 1990. Forest management and wildlife conservation in Central America: what are the options? V International Congress of Ecology-First International Symposium on Wildlife Conservation. Tsukuba and Yokohama, Japan. Aug. 21-25, 1990. *

Korn, H. 1990. Importance of small mammals in the structure and functioning of ecosystems. Deutsche Gesellschaft fuer Saugetierkunde. Osnabrueck, Germany. Sept. 23-27, 1990.

Liske, J. 1991. Ecotourism and the scarlet macaw in Carara Biological Reserve, Costa Rica: a case for commensalism? First Mesoamerican Workshop on Conservation and Management of Macaws. Tegucigalpa, Honduras. Jan. 4-7, 1991.

McCoy, M. 1991. Ecology and management perspectives for the scarlet macaw (*Ara macao*) in Carara Biological Reserve, Costa Rica. First Mesoamerican Workshop on Conservation and Management of Macaws. Tegucigalpa, Honduras. Jan. 4-7, 1991.

Barrasa, L. 1991. Environmental education for white-tailed deer conservation in a rural Costa Rican community. I Panamerican Congress on Wildlife Conservation through Education. Caracas, Venezuela. Jan. 23-27, 1991. *

López, N. 1991. Red-and-blue macaw nest conservation in Concepción Department, Paraguay. I Panamerican Congress on Wildlife Conservation through Education. Caracas, Venezuela. Jan. 23-27, 1991. *

Rodríguez, S. 1991. Agrarian conservationist policies in the natural protected areas of Costa Rica: conservation or contradiction? XVII Conference of the Latin American Studies Association. Washington, D.C. Apr. 4-6, 1991.

López, N. 1991. Factors which affect psittacid populations and species exploitation by rural communities. I Ornithological Meeting between Argentina, Paraguay and Brazil. Ciudad del Este, Paraguay. May 8-11, 1991.

McCoy, M., & J. M. Rodríguez. 1991. Cattail eradication methods in the restoration of a tropical seasonal, freshwater marsh. Third Annual Conference of the Society for Ecological Restoration. Orlando, Florida. May 20-23, 1991. *

Carrillo, E. 1991. Movement patterns and food habits of the racoon (*Procyon lotor*) in Manuel Antonio National Park, Costa Rica. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *

DiMare, M. 1991. Food habits of the white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) in San Lucas Island, Costa Rica. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *

Espach, H. 1991. Movement, home-range, activity and diet of captive white-tailed deer fawns (*Odocoileus virginianus*) upon release. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *

- Hernández, L. 1991. Extension and environmental education in white-tailed deer management in Costa Rica. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *
- Irby, L. 1991. White-tailed deer management in Montana, USA. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *
- Irby, L. 1991. Habitat use by white-tailed deer in the southern Nicoyan Peninsula, Costa Rica. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *
- Navarro, S. 1991. Biology, ecology and utilization of the lowland trout (*Agronostomus monticola*) in the Sierra de Manantlán Biosphere Reserve, México. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *
- Rodríguez, M. 1991. The life cycle of the white-tailed deer in San Lucas Island, Costa Rica. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *
- Rodríguez, M. 1991. Social group size and composition in the white-tailed deer herd on San Lucas Island, Costa Rica. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *
- Attending professional meetings has permitted PRMVS faculty and students to contribute, network, and learn what is happening worldwide in the biodiversity-wildlife management field.*
- Sáenz, J. 1991. White-tailed deer reintroduction in Northwest Costa Rica. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *
- Vaughan, C. 1991. Genetic variation in a white-tailed deer population. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *
- Vaughan, C. 1991. Management of the white-tailed deer herd on San Lucas Island, Costa Rica. III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *
- Wong, G. 1991. Conservation of the squirrel monkey in Costa Rica. III International Natural Resource and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. May 21-24, 1991. *
- Wong, G. 1991. Study and conservation of primates in Costa Rica. Interamerican Meeting of Primatology. Veracruz, México. Jun. 24-27, 1991. *
- Thompson, L., C. Mo, M. Oviedo, J. Homan, and the Interamerican Bluetongue Team. 1991. Prevalence and incidence of Bluetongue virus in the Caribbean Basin: serologic and virologic findings. II Symposium on Bluetongue, African Swine Disease and Related Orbivirus. Paris, France. Jun. 17-21, 1991. **
- Greiner, E., C. Mo, V. Tanya, L. Thompson, M. Oviedo and the Interamerican Bluetongue Team. 1991. Review of clinical bluetongue disease in Central America and the Caribbean. II Symposium on Bluetongue, African Swine Disease and Related Orbivirus. Paris, France. Jun. 17-21, 1991. **
- McCoy, M., J. M. Rodríguez, & J. L. Altuve. 1991. Reproductive success and population increase of black-bellied whistling ducks (*Dendrocygna autumnalis*) in newly placed artificial nests in a tropical freshwater marsh. "Wildlife 2001: Populations", an International Conference on Population Dynamics and Management of Vertebrates (Exclusive of Primates and Fish). Oakland, California. Jul. 29-31, 1991. *
- Mo, C. 1991. Ecology of bluetongue viruses in the American tropics. XXIV World Veterinary Medical Congress. Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. Aug. 18-23, 1991. *
- Korn, H. 1991. Genetic, demographic, spatial, environmental and catastrophic effects on the survival probability of small populations of mammals. German National Mammalogy Congress. Hamburg, Germany.
- Vaughan, C. 1991. Conserving biodiversity: interfaces with animal production. International Symposium/Workshop Livestock and Natural Resources in Central America: Strategies for Sustainability. CATIE. San José, Costa Rica. Oct. 7-12, 1991. *
- March, I. 1991. Evaluation of habitat and present status of the white-lipped peccary (*Tayassu pecari*) in México. XI National Zoology Congress. Mérida, México. Oct. 28-31, 1991.
- March, I. 1991. The present situation in the study, management and conservation of wildlife in southwest México: a personal opinion. XI National Zoology Congress. Mérida, México. Oct. 28-31, 1991.
- López, N. 1991. Distribution and relative density of psittacids in three vegetative associations of Concepción

PRESENTATIONS AT PROFESSIONAL MEETINGS (Continued)

- Department, Paraguay. IV Neotropical Ornithological Congress. Quito, Ecuador. Nov. 3-9, 1991. *
- López, N. 1991. Requisites and nesting site availability for psittacids in Concepción Department, Paraguay. IV Neotropical Ornithological Congress. Quito, Ecuador. Nov. 3-9, 1991. *
- López, N. 1991. Importance of ornithological collections in bird inventories and biological conservation. IV Neotropical Ornithological Congress. Quito, Ecuador. Nov. 3-9, 1991. *
- Márquez, C. 1991. Composition and distribution of diurnal raptors in Palo Verde National Park, Costa Rica. IV Neotropical Ornithological Congress. Quito, Ecuador. Nov. 3-9, 1991. *
- Rau, J., D. Martínez, M. Tillería and J. Low. 1991. Predation by grey foxes on small mammals in a primary growth rainforest of Southern Chile: role of field protocols. XXXIV Annual Meeting of the Chilean Biology Society. Puyehue, Osorno, Chile. Nov. 1991. *
- Chalukian, S. 1991. Data bases to evaluate the effects of habitat alteration, principally by fire, on wildlife in Palo Verde, Costa Rica. Third National Biology Congress. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 18-22, 1991. *
- Fallas, J. 1991. Wildlife habitat classification using a low-cost geographical information system. Third National Biology Congress. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 18-22, 1991. *
- Márquez, C. 1991. Composition and distribution of diurnal raptors in Palo Verde National Park, Costa Rica. Third National Biology Congress. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 18-22, 1991. *
- McCoy, M., & J. M. Rodríguez. 1991. Cattail eradication methods in the restoration of a tropical seasonal, freshwater marsh. Third National Biology Congress. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 18-22, 1991. *
- McCoy, M., J. M. Rodríguez, & J. L. Altuve. 1991. Reproductive success and population increase of black-bellied whistling ducks (*Dendrocygna autumnalis*) in newly placed artificial nests in a tropical freshwater marsh. Third National Biology Congress. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 18-22, 1991. *
- Vides, R. 1991. Birds as bioindicators in the design of buffer zones in natural reserves in the subtropical mountainous forests in Argentina. Third National Biology Congress. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 18-22, 1991. *
- Mo, C. 1992. Microorganism infection of olive ridley sea turtle eggs. XII Workshop on Conservation and Biology of Marine Turtles. Jeckyll Island, Georgia. February, 1992. *
- Carrillo, E. 1992. Tourism and its influence on wildlife conservation in protected areas. Second International Symposium on Ecology, Tourism and Municipalities. Hotel Herradura, Costa Rica. May, 1992. *
- Wong, G. 1992. Effect of tourism on squirrel monkey populations of Manuel Antonio National Park. Second International Symposium on Ecology, Tourism and Municipalities. Hotel Herradura, Costa Rica. May, 1992. *
- McCoy, M. & J. M. Rodríguez. 1992. Cattail eradication methods in the restoration of a tropical seasonal, freshwater marsh. IV International Wetlands Conference. Columbus, Ohio. September 13-18, 1992. *
- McCoy, M. 1992. Efficiency of explosive mechanical alarms in the reduction of damage to irrigated rice by black-bellied whistling ducks (*Dendrocygna autumnalis*) in Guanacaste, Costa Rica. First Central American Congress on Entomology and Natural Control of Pests. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 16-20, 1992. *
- Monge, J. 1992. Feasibility of integrated pest management for vertebrate species. First Central American Congress on Entomology and Natural Control of Pests. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 16-20, 1992. *
- Monge, J. 1992. Importance of biological and ecological information in vertebrate pest management. First Central American Congress on Entomology and Natural Control of Pests. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 16-20, 1992. *
- Monge, J. 1992. The cotton rat (*Sigmodon hispidus*): control alternatives. First Central American Congress on Entomology and natural control of pests. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 16-20, 1992. *
- Fallas, J. 1992. Initial growth of *Gmelina arborea* in Las Delicias de Rio Claro, Golfito, Puntarenas. II National Forestry Congress. San José, Costa Rica. Nov. 25-27, 1992.
- Bonino, N. 1992. Home range, habitat use and daily activity of *Orthogeomys heterodus* (Rodentia, Geomyidae) in a horticultural zone of Costa Rica. I Latin American Theriology Congress. Caracas, Venezuela. Dec. 7-11, 1992. *
- Rau, J. R. 1992. Correlational and experimental evidence of key predation by "gray foxes" on competing rodents in temperate forested ecosystems. I Latin American Congress of Theriology. Caracas, Venezuela. Dec. 7-11, 1992. *

STAFF AND STUDENT PUBLICATIONS 1987-1992

In developing countries, research and especially publication of results of scientific studies is uncommon. Conditions and stimulus for such don't exist. The fact that PRMVS staff and students have been highly successful in both, testifies to the positive professional environment at PRMVS. Graduates are continuing this method of communication upon return to their countries. PRMVS will continue to stimulate professional advancement with such events as the International Wildlife Management Congress in Costa Rica during September 19-25, 1993, the re-initiation of the journal, Vida Silvestre Neotropical, and a technical report series within PRMVS.

- Alberts, A., T. Sharp, D. Werner and P. Weldon. 1992. Seasonal variation of lipids in femoral gland secretions of male green iguanas (*Iguana iguana*). *Journal of Chemical Ecology* 18(5):703-712.
- Allen, M. E., O. Oftedal and D. Werner. 1990. Management of the green iguana (*Iguana iguana*) in Central America. Pages 19-22 in *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the American Assoc. of Zoo Veterin.* South Padre Island, Texas.
- Allsteadt, J. and C. Vaughan. 1988. Distress call of caiman (*Caiman crocodilus fuscus*) in Caño Negro Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 36:567-568.
- Allsteadt, J. and C. Vaughan. 1988. Ecological studies of the Central American caiman (*Caiman crocodilus fuscus*) in Caño Negro National Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica. *Bull. Chicago Herpet. Soc.* 23(8):123-126.
- Aranda, M. 1991. Wild mammal skin trade in Chiapas, México. Pages 174-177 in J. Robinson and K. Redford (eds.), *Neotropical Wildlife: Use and Conservation.* The University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL. 520 pp.
- Beltrán, J., M. Delibes and J. Rau. 1991. Methods of censusing red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) populations. *Hystrix* 3:199-214.
- Bonino, N. and A. Pelliza Sbriller. 1991. Botanical composition of the guanaco diet in two contrasting environments in Tierra del Fuego, Argentina. *Ecología Austral* 1(2):97-102.
- Bonino, N. and L. Hilje. 1992. Estimation of the abundance of the pocket gopher *Orthogeomys heterodus* (Rodentia, Geomyidae) and the damage produced in a horticultural area of Costa Rica. *Manejo Integrado de Plagas* 23:26-31.
- Bonino, N. and L. Hilje. 1992. Comparison of two methods of control of the pocket gopher *Orthogeomys heterodus* (Rodentia, Geomyidae) in Costa Rica. *Manejo Integrado de Plagas* 23:39-45.
- Buffa, J. and D. Werner. 1989. Riparian habitat protection and reforestation in Panamá and Costa Rica to enhance food production and wildlife. Pages 441-444 in *Proceedings of the International Wetland Symposium.* Charleston, South Carolina.
- Carbonell, M. and V. Lichstein. 1991. Estrategia de Conservación de la Argentina. World Wildlife Fund.
- Carrillo E. and C. Vaughan. 1989. Rainfall influence on raccoon movements in a Costa Rican cloud forest. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 36(2B):373-376.
- Fallas, J. 1989. Environmental impact study: Fortuna Aporte Project. Hydrological Component. Tropical Science Center, San José, Costa Rica. 28 pp.
- Fallas, J. 1989. Geographic information systems: a new technology for natural resource planning. Pages 65-77 in III National Hydrological Resource Congress. San José, Costa Rica.
- Fallas, J. 1990. Map-for-the-PC: a geographical information system for IBM and compatible microcomputers. III Venezuelan Geography Congress. Mérida, Venezuela. 17 pp.
- Fallas, J. 1991. Environmental impact study: Angostura project. Hydrological component. Tropical Science Center, San José, Costa Rica. 60 pp.
- A total of 96 publications were produced by 15 professors and eight students. These included 11 books or parts therein, 44 journal articles, 24 works produced by scientific meetings, and 17 technical reports.***
- Fallas, J. and R. Sánchez. 1991. Changes in land use, politics in watershed management and its impact on flooding in Costa Rica. Final Report on Risk Zones and Natural Disasters of the Central American Research Program of the Superior Council of the Central American Univer. (CSUCA). 78 pp.
- Fallas, J. and C. Valverde. 1989. Potential site selection for reforestation with cypress (*Cupressus lusitanica* Mill) using a geographical information system of low cost. I Cartographic Model. Pages 447-475 in II Latin American Conference on Technology of Geographic Information Systems (GIS). Mérida, Venezuela.
- Fallas, J. and C. Valverde. 1989. Rainfall erosion in May from the Juan Santamaria Pluviological Station, Alajuela, Costa Rica. Pages 78-85 in *Proceedings of III National Hydrological Resource Congress.* San José, Costa Rica.
- Frazier, J. 1990. International Resource Conservation: Where's the Challenge? *Transactions 55th North American Wildlife and Natural Resources Conference.* Denver, Colorado.

- Frazier, J. 1990. Marine turtles in Chile: An update. Pages 39-41 in T. Richardson, J. Richardson and M. Donnelly (eds.), Proc. of the X Annual Workshop on Sea Turtle Biology and Conservation. NOAA Tech. Memorandum NMFSSSEFC-278. Nat. Marine Fisheries Serv., Miami, FL. 286 pp.
- Fullerton, R. and J. Fallas. 1991. Environmental assessment: Palo Verde National Park, Costa Rica. Pages 13-91 in GIS/LIS 91 Conference. Atlanta, Georgia.
- Gow, D., R. Bolaños, L. Bonnefil, C. Donato, G. Hartshorn, J. Laarman, D. Norman, J. Tolisano, and J. Tosi. 1988. Environmental assessment for the northern zone consolidation project in Costa Rica. Volume I: Environmental Assessment. Development Strategies for Fragile Lands, Washington, D. C. 102 pp.
- Hilje, L. 1992. Biology and control of rodent pests in Costa Rica. *Manejo Integrado de Plagas* 23:17-25.
- Hilje, L. 1992. Damage and control of rodent pests in Costa Rica. *Manejo Integrado de Plagas* 23:32-38.
- Hilje, L. and J. Monge. 1988. Preliminary diagnostic about vertebrates as pests in Costa Rica. Publications Department, Universidad Nacional, Heredia, Costa Rica. 17 pp.
- Hilje, L. and J. Monge. 1990. Preliminary list and general considerations about vertebrate pests in Costa Rica. *Manejo Integrado de Plagas* 10:39-52.
- Hilje, L., C. Araya, F. Scorza and M. Víquez. 1991. Forest plagues and diseases in Central America: consulting manual. Technical Series. Technical Manual No. 3. Centro Agronómico Tropical de Investigación y Enseñanza, Turrialba, Costa Rica. 187 pp.
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- Homan, J., C. Mo, L. Thompson, C. Barreto, M. Oviedo, E. Gibbs and E. Greiner. 1990. Epidemiologic study of bluetongue viruses in Central America and the Caribbean: 1986-1988. *J. American Vet. Med. Ass.* 51:(7)1089-1094.
- Korn, H. 1987. Effects of live-trapping and toe-clipping on body weight of European and African rodent species. *Oecologia* 71:597-600.
- Korn, H. 1989. A feeding experiment with 6-methoxybenzoxolone and a wild population of the deer mouse, *Peromyscus maniculatus*. *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 67:2220-2224.
- Korn, H. 1989. The annual cycle in body weight of small mammals from the Transvaal, South Africa, as an adaptation to a subtropical seasonal environment. *Journal of Zoology (London)* 218:223-231.
- Korn, H. (ed.). 1990. Population Ecology Course. Universidad Nacional. Heredia, Costa Rica. 233 pp.
- Korn, H. 1991. Small mammals and the mosaic cycle concept of ecosystems. Pages 106-131 in H. Remmert (ed.), *The Mosaic-cycle Concept of Ecosystems*. Ecological Studies 85. Springer-Verlag.
- Korn, H. 1991. Rapid repopulation by small mammals of an area isolated by roads. *Mammalia* 55:629-632.
- Korn, H. 1992. Unused vs. used traps in small mammal population studies. *Saugetierkundl. Mitt* 34:65-68.
- Korn, H. and L. Braack. 1987. Survival of wild gerbils (*Mammalia: Rodentia*) parasitized by larvae of the blowfly (*Cordylobia anthropophaga*, Insecta: Diptera). *Z. f. Saugetierkunde* 52:56-57.
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- Korn, H. and U. Korn. 1989. The effects of gerbils (*Taterus brantsii*) on primary production and plant species composition in a southern African savanna. *Oecologia* 79:271-278.
- Kriek, W. and E. Vargas. 1991. Forestry extension: key activity in the solution of the environmental problem. Pages 67-80 in B. Gracia (ed.), *Environmental Deterioration in Costa Rica: Balance and Perspectives*. University of Costa Rica, San Pedro de Montes de Oca, Costa Rica. 305 pp.
- López, N. 1990. Rare types and their importance in biological conservation. *Nuestras Aves* 21:9-10.
- López, N. 1991. Use of forests in Paraguay: Focus on legal regimes. *Flora, Fauna y Areas Silvestres* 5(13):10-12.
- Lyons, J. and S. Navarro. 1990. Fishes of the Sierra de Manantlán, west-central, México. *The Southwestern Naturalist* 35(1):32-46.
- March, I. 1990. Monographie des Weibbartpekaris (*Tayassu pecari*). *Bongo (Berlin)* 18:151-170.
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- McCoy, M. B., J. M. Rodríguez, & J. L. Altuve. 1992. Reproductive success and population increase of black-bellied whistling ducks (*Dendrocygna autumnalis*) in newly placed artificial nests in a tropical freshwater marsh. Pages 653-664 in D. R. McCullough & R. H. Barrett (eds.), *Wildlife 2001: Populations*. Elsevier Science Publishers, Ltd. London, England. 1163 pp.

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- Norman, D. 1991. La Lorita. Environmental Education Magazine No. 1. The Nursery and the Planting of Trees. Impresión Comercial La Nación, San José, Costa Rica. 24 pp. with poster.
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"With the inauguration, today, of this first Wildlife Documentation Center in Latin America, we open a new era of communication which can only benefit neotropical wildlife and its human stewards..."

-Prince Philip, Duke of Edinburgh
President of World Wildlife Fund for Nature
United Kingdom

February 1, 1988 (at BIODOC's inauguration)

OUTREACH THROUGH INFORMATION AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER

BIODOC

In October of 1987, the Wildlife Documentation Center (BIODOC) was established with assistance from the United States Fish and Wildlife Service. It was officially inaugurated on February 1, 1988 by Prince Philip, Duke of Edinburgh and President of the World Wildlife Fund for Nature and Dr. Carlos Araya Pochet, President of the Universidad Nacional.

BIODOC is oriented to assist the bibliographical needs of researchers, professors and students by providing books, scientific journals, reprints, bulletins, theses and unpublished "gray" literature concerning wildlife from all over the world, with emphasis in the neotropics.

Wildlife research in Latin America is facing two major problems from an information point of view: a) limited access to the existing scientific literature because of elevated book and journal subscription costs and a lack of libraries and specialized centers, and b) limited access to literature from developing countries because many of these country's researchers don't publish their results, which instead are presented as "gray literature" or reports to universities, governmental or non-governmental agencies with limited distribution.

Therefore many Latin American scientists repeat research projects or are not aware of "state-of-the-art" investigation because of a lack of access to the conventional and unconventional literature.

Objectives. The general objective of BIODOC is to recover and systematize the existing wildlife literature in Latin America, making it available to users. Specific objectives include: a) maintain organized and up-to-date bibliographical material; b) facilitate an excellent library collection, c) establish a reference and consultation service for Latin American professionals outside of Costa Rica, d) establish an information network to obtain

"gray literature" in Latin America, and e) inform the public about recent acquisitions through three bulletins; recent book purchases (monthly), periodic publications (yearly), and "gray literature" (yearly).

Services. BIODOC offers the following services:

- **loan** Reading room loan of books, journals, "gray literature", periodical publications, reprints which cover the wildlife field;
- **books** Over 3000 book titles on ecology, biology and management of birds, mammals, reptiles, amphibians, and plants;
- **scientific journals** Complete collections of several scientific journals (The Journal of Wildlife Management, Ecology, Journal of Mammalogy, Auk, Ecological Monographs, The Wilson Bulletin), partial collection of 270 others and subscriptions to 79 scientific journals;

- **reprints** Over 7000 reprints of wildlife related articles on file;

- **abstracts** Two important collections make BIODOC one of the most up-to-date wildlife documentation centers. The complete collection of Wildlife Review (1935-1992) and Zoological Record from 1974-1992 for reptiles, birds, mammals and amphibians;

- **"gray literature"** Over 1200 Latin American research projects are found in BIODOC, including technical reports, institutional reports, and theses (licenciature, master, and doctorate);

- **computerized data bases** The complete set of citations found in Wildlife Review plus our 7000 reprints and 700 "gray literature" documents are offered on one compact disk accessible with a "user friendly" database microcomputer program which can retrieve citations by scientific name, author name, geographical region, or keywords

- **bulletin archive** BIODOC receives many reports from NGOs and other conservation groups;
- **documental archive** To complement the bibliographical information, BIODOC offers an archive of over 4000 Costa Rican newspaper clippings related to this theme;
- **interlibrary loan** This service is offered between other libraries in Costa Rica;
- **foreign requests** Up to 10 reprints per request and computerized searches of wildlife themes are mailed to solicitors. BIODOC is studying the possibility of sending larger documents if prepaid.

Products

- **Informative Bulletin** Edited every three months and sent to over 150 centers and interested persons. Contains a list of the latest acquisitions of Biodoc.
- **Journal Bulletin** Edited once a year and sent to the same centers and interested persons. Contains a printout of all new journals' table of contents.
- **"Gray literature" Bulletin** Edited once a year and sent to the same centers and interested persons. Contains a list of the "gray literature" available in BIODOC.

Professional Staff

Enrique Quesada: Coordinator
 Nidia Durán: Document Analyst
 Lilliana Quesada: Librarian Technician

Remote Sensing and Geographical Information Systems

Precise, accessible and opportune information is essential to formulate, divulge and execute any management plan in the natural resource field. Actually, the limiting factor is not the absence of information but its storage, actualization and manipulation in an intelligent and efficient manner.

The second half of the 1980's has been characterized by major advances in the microcomputer field. Word processors, electronic sheets and data bases, once restricted to mainframes and mini-computers in the 1970's, are actually accessible to most users at a low cost. Microcomputer use has permitted researchers and planners to process and analyze their data more quickly, efficiently and at a lower cost.

Modern society requires that the professional in wildlife management manipulate, analyze and integrate a large volume of information; much of which is already, or should be expressed, in cartographic form. The geographical information systems (GIS) were developed to give the professional an efficient and precise medium to store, process, integrate and visualize biophysical, socio-economical, and cultural variables.

The use of maps for analytical purposes is a recent and relatively little used technique in the planning and monitoring of natural resources in Latin America. Even though computers offer an efficient and precise medium to manipulate and analyze large volumes of information, GIS is still little known and absent in the processes of environmental planning, design and monitoring in Latin America. Frequently, a limiting factor in the use of that technology is the lack of economic and human resources to install and maintain costly and sophisticated systems.

Jorge Fallas

BIODOC has served over 6500 users from 1988-92 at its installations.

PRMVS has placed special emphasis on the establishment of a Remote Sensing and Geographical Information Systems Laboratory (TELESIG) which permits our students to acquire first-hand experience with this new technology. To date, PRMVS has acquired three computers with 80486 processors of 33 and 50 Mhz; which are equipped with high resolution video systems, 1.2 Gbyte hard disks, an EXABYTE 8 mm tape system and 88 Mbyte Syquest removable disk system. For digital image processing, we have the AGIS (Advanced Geographical Information System) donated by Delta Data System, Inc.), DRAGON, IDRISI, OSU-MAP and CI/SIG programs. To enter data, a Summagraphics MicroGrid III digitizing table (1.44 by 1.12 meters) is available. The generated products can be printed using a HIP XL-300 color laser printer. An agreement signed with Middle Tennessee State University accesses TELESIG to a electrostatic printer for the production of final maps. We also have a Trimble Geographical Positioning System (GPS) base station.

Microcomputer Training

Students. The microcomputer explosion has transformed the lives of almost everyone, including our Latin American students. The importance of these machines to future scientists, managers and administrators is immense.

Computer Center of PRMVS for student use.

Since many tasks are made easier by use of computers; word-processing, data analysis, desktop publishing, etc. we have placed much emphasis on training students in use of these methods. PRMVS facilitated a microcomputer laboratory in 1987. It now holds 9 microcomputers; eight 80286 micros (12-20 Mhz) with 40 Mbyte hard disks and one 8088

PC/XT, and three dot-matrix printers. Also available are three laptop

Fifth promotion students analyzing data during field course at Palo Verde National Park.

portable micros for use in the field during field courses or other related activities.

Professors. Currently, professors of PRMVS share 4 desktop micros for daily activities. More purchases are necessary for faculty.

Administration. All three secretaries, the administrative assistant, and budget coordinator have individual microcomputers with 20-40 Mbyte hard disks to use in their tasks. The administrators have taken various courses on use of word-processing, spreadsheets and databases.

Scientific Journal, "Vida Silvestre Neotropical"

In 1986, World Wildlife Fund-US and U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service initiated the production of a technical scientific journal "Vida Silvestre Neotropical", as an international outlet for publication of research results by Latin American scientists, managers and administrators in the wildlife and wildlands management fields. Up to 1990, a total of four numbers were produced including 29 main articles and 14 short communications of excellent quality. Unfortunately, due to time constraints of WWF employees involved, the journal was discontinued in 1990.

In late 1991 a call for proposals was sent out by a consortium (WWF-US, USFWS, Wildlife Conservation International) of interested organizations willing to finance the re-initiation of the journal. PRMVS

submitted a proposal, after unsuccessful efforts to start the journal in South American institutions. In October 1992 PRMVS was awarded the grant to undertake this project. Michael McCoy and Christopher Vaughan will be editors and direct the effort. Claudette Mo and Jaime Rau will be assistant editors.

The money is to finance only the first three years of this process, with a major objective that the journal be financially self-sufficient after that. Activities were initiated in January 1993 with the goal of yearly publication of two numbers, one in June and another by December.

The proposed objectives of the journal will be the following: "The journal should serve the needs of professionals, technicians and students and, to a lesser extent, decision-makers in the region. Therefore, it should contain a broad scope of geographic coverage and topics. Geographically, the journal should serve the information needs of Mexico, Central America, the Caribbean, and South America. Subject areas should include wild fauna and flora; terrestrial, freshwater and marine habitats; and research and management of species (including natural forests), ecosystems and wildlands." Additionally, we accept manuscripts in Spanish, Portuguese or English and use the same format rules as the original journal.

We will readily accept any potential manuscripts for consideration at this time. ♡

Eduardo Carrillo

DOCUMENTARY FILMS AND SLIDE SHOWS

PRMVS has been active in publicizing its conservation efforts via short documentaries, which augments our student's skills in this important medium.

● **"New Horizons for the White-tailed Deer; I".** Documentary on research and management on this species in Guanacaste Province, Costa Rica. Made in 1988 by Patricia Sánchez of National System of Radio and Television (SINART, Costa Rica) with assistance from Vivienne Solís and aired on national television in December 1988. (20 minutes)

Christopher Vaughan

Captured deer fawn is readied for transport.

● **"Regional Wildlife Management Program for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean".** Audiovisual slide-tape program made by Lewis and Wilma Nelson in 1989 with assistance from the Organization of American States. (25 minutes)

● **"Palo Verde".** Documentary on restoration efforts in 1989 for this marsh. Made by Mariano Rodríguez, Teletica Canal 7, San José Costa Rica with assistance from Michael McCoy and aired on national television nightly news program in May 1989. (10 minutes)

Michael McCoy

Cattail is cut with side-bar mower underwater for re-establishment of better habitat for waterfowl.

● **"New Horizons for the White-tailed Deer; II".** Documentary on research and management of this species in Guanacaste province, Costa Rica. Made in 1990 by Patricia Sánchez of National System of Radio and Television (SINART, Costa Rica) with assistance from Vivienne Solís and aired on national television in 1990. (25 minutes)

● **"Palo Verde Marsh".** Documentary on the importance of the Palo Verde marsh for aquatic birds and the management efforts underway in its restoration. Made by

Patricia Sánchez of the National System of Radio and Television (SINART, Costa Rica) with assistance from Michael McCoy and aired on national television in June, 1990. (15 minutes)

● **"Conservation of the Scarlet Macaw in Carara Biological Reserve".** Documentary on research on this species by PRMVS. Made by Patricia Sánchez of National System of Radio and Television (SINART, Costa Rica) with assistance from Christopher Vaughan and aired on national television in June, 1990. (15 minutes)

● **"So That I am Not Forgotten; the Squirrel Monkey".** Documentary on thesis work by Grace Wong in Manuel Antonio National Park on the ecology of this monkey. Made in 1991 by the Audio-Visual Department of the National Correspondence University, San José (UNED) with assistance from Grace Wong and aired on national television on September, 1991. (11 minutes)

● **"Coatimundi Natural History in Tropical Dry Forest".** Documentary on research on coatimundi as seed disperser and reforester in Guanacaste National Park, Costa Rica. Made in 1992 by the British Broadcasting Corporation with the aid of Joel Sáenz and to be aired on worldwide television in early 1993.

Marcelo Aranda

● **"A Place for Everyone; Corcovado National Park".** Documentary on the importance of this biological gem for biodiversity conservation. Made by the Audio-Visual Department of the National Correspondence University, San José (UNED) with assistance from Eduardo Carrillo and aired on national television in May, 1992. (20 minutes)

Eduardo Carrillo

● **"Regional Wildlife Management Program for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean".** Update on earlier audiovisual slide-tape program made by Claudette Mo in 1992 with assistance from PRMVS. (25 minutes)

SHORT-COURSES AND WORKSHOPS 1987-1992

March-April, 1988. Graduate field course "Neotropical Vertebrate Ecology". **C. Vaughan and E. Carrillo** (coordinators). Organization for Tropical Studies-PRMVS. Most PRMVS academic staff and 15 other resource people participated. (Attendance 15 students from 8 Latin American countries).

July 19-22, 1988. Short course. **C. Vaughan and C. Mo**. "Cervid capture and handling". CESP-Electrical Company of Sao Paulo, Brazil. (Attendance 10).

November 1988-July 1989. 8 Workshops. **L. and W. Nelson**. Environmental Education. Part of the I Central American Biology Congress, Guatemala. (Attendance 55). Country Day School, Costa Rica. (Attendance 18 teachers). Biology Department of Universidad Autónoma de Honduras. (Attendance 30 students and 5 professors). Universidad del Valle, Guatemala. (Attendance 12 professors, 1 teacher, 1 student, 1 priest). Colegio Metropolitano, Guatemala. (Attendance 21 teachers, 1 superintendent). PRMVS, Costa Rica. (Attendance 8 PRMVS students and 18 other students). Lincoln School, Costa Rica. (7 teachers). Biology Department of Universidad Nacional Autónoma de Honduras. (Attendance 15 students and 2 professors).

April 1-28, 1989. Course. **J. Frazier**. Wildlife Conservation and Management Training. Smithsonian Institution and FUDENA, Venezuela. (Attendance 10 students from 5 countries).

June 7-August 9, 1989. Fieldcourse. **J. Frazier**. IX International Course in Techniques in Conservation and Management of Wildlife. Organized by the Smithsonian Institution. Front Royal, Virginia. (Attendance 22 students from 17 countries).

September 1989. Workshop. **J. Fallas**. Application of Geographical Information Systems in Planning and Monitoring of Natural Resources. University of San Carlos, Guatemala. (Attendance 15).

October 31-November 6, 1989. Workshop. **M. González, N. López, C. Vaughan**. Invited specialists in the First Workshop for the Planning of a Graduate Program in Wildlife Conservation for the Southern Cone. Buenos Aires, Argentina. (Attendance 40).

December 2-8, 1989. Workshop. **D. Werner** (coordinator). International Advisory Group for Foundation Iguana Verde. Costa Rica.

March 23, 1990. Course and seminar. **I. March**. "The role of environmental education in wildlife management". Course on Environmental Education. PRONATURA-Project Wild. San Cristobal de las Casas, Mexico. (Attendance 25).

September 1990. **E. Quesada**. Organization of the wildlife documentation center at the Graduate Program in Wildlife Management in the National Experimental University of the Western Plains, Ezequiel Zamora. Guanare, Portuguesa, Venezuela.

October 8-12, 1990. Shortcourse. **C. Mo and D. Forrester**. Wildlife Parasitology. Graduate students from PRMVS and Veterinary Medicine School, UNA. (Attendance 15).

First Promotion students in the Wildlife Parasitology short-course.

December 3-6, 1990. Workshop. First Mesoamerican Wildlife Management Workshop. La Selva Biological Station, Costa Rica. **E. Carrillo** (coordinator). (Attendance of 1-3 biologists from each of Mesoamerican countries. Papers presented on wildlife-biodiversity status by following persons: **E. Carrillo** (Costa Rica), **A. Cruz** (Honduras), **G. Cruz** (Nicaragua), **M. González** (Guatemala), **I. March** (Mexico), **O. Rosado** (Belice), **A. Sermeño** (El Salvador), **J. Ventocilla** (Panama). A strategy for regional wildlife-biodiversity conservation was discussed and proceedings are being edited.

A total of seven short-courses, and 19 workshops were given by 9 professors and nine graduates of PRMVS. Over 650 people received these courses covering environmental education, geographical information systems, wildlife management techniques, management plans and graduate program development.

December 12-17, 1990. Excursion. **D. Werner**. II Festival of the Iguana Verde. Students, professors, and administrative people from PRMVS went to Llano Grande de Ocu, Provincia de Herrera, Panama to observe the research-extension work carried out by the Iguana Verde Foundation. (Attendance 50).

April 23-26, 1991. Conference/Workshop. All PRMVS staff participated. First Latinamerican Conference of Graduate Programs in Wildlife Management. **C. Vaughan, M. Carranza and J. Barrantes** (coordinators). (Attendance 40 with 2-3 delegates from the wildlife management graduate programs in Venezuela, Brazil and Argentina; donors and PRMVS staff and students).

May 21-24, 1991. Symposium. First Latin American Symposium on White-tailed Deer. Part of III International Natural Resources and Wildlife Symposium. Guadalajara, México. **C. Vaughan and M. Rodríguez** (co-organizers). Six PRMVS staff and graduate students participated. (Attendance 35).

August, 1991. Short Course. **C. Mo**. "Epidemiology of wildlife diseases". Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Sao Paulo, Brazil. (Attendance 77 veterinarians and students).

April 1-3, 1992. Workshop. **M. Carbonell and M. McCoy**. Research priorities for Palo Verde National Park. Organized by PACA and Ministry of Natural Resources, Energy and Mines. Palo Verde National Park, Costa Rica. (Attendance 50).

July 12, 1992. Workshop. **M. McCoy**. "Environmental Education - Project Wild Activities". Ecology High School. Monteverde, Costa Rica. (Attendance 25).

November 9-11, 1992. Workshop. **J. Fallas**. "Geographic information systems: principles and application to natural resource management". PRMVS. II National Forestry Congress. San José, Costa Rica. (Attendance 12).

November 24, 1992. Seminar/Workshop. **M. Rodríguez, E. Carrillo and C. Vaughan** (coordinators), **Marcela Aranda** (guest specialist). Analysis of the jaguar situation in Costa Rica and perspectives for its management. Jointly carried out by PRMVS-Costa Rican Wildlife Service. UNA. Heredia, Costa Rica. (Attendance 20).

SEMINARS 1987-1992

November 1987. **D. Norman.** "Minimum critical areas for conservation of genetic diversity", "Wildlife status and management tendencies in Central America", and "A review of wildlife management principles". International Mobile Seminar in Wildlands Management. Centro Agronómico Tropical de Investigación y Enseñanza. Turrialba, Costa Rica. (Attendance 30).

Of the more than 100 seminars given by PRMVS staff and graduates from 1987-92, this is a sample of 38 seminars given by 11 professors and two graduates to over 1200 listeners.

February 1988. **D. Werner.** "Green iguana management in captivity". Meeting of the Survival Service Commission. IUCN General Assembly, San Jose, Costa Rica. (Attendance 200).

February 1988. **C. Vaughan.** "Wildlife graduate program in Latin America". Meeting of the Survival Service Commission. IUCN General Assembly. San Jose, Costa Rica. (Attendance 200).

July 1988. **D. Norman.** "Principles of wildlife management". XI Annual Course on Wildland Planning and Management. Centro Agronómico Tropical de Investigación y Enseñanza. Turrialba, Costa Rica. (Attendance 28).

August 1988. **D. Norman.** "The Tupinambis lizard as a management candidate in the Southern Cone and the utilization of this resource for the rural populations of Paraguay". XI Annual Course on Wildland Planning and Management. Centro Agronómico Tropical de Investigación y Enseñanza. Turrialba, Costa Rica. (Attendance 28).

March 9, 1989. **C. Vaughan.** "Ecology and management of white-tailed deer in Costa Rica". Institute of Ecology, Mexico, Mexico. (Attendance 10).

May 1989. **E. Carrillo.** "Raccoon ecology in Costa Rica". International Course on Wildlife Refuge Management. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service-Costa Rican Wildlife Service. Palo Verde National Wildlife Refuge, Costa Rica. (Attendance 30).

September 25-October 9, 1989. **D. Werner.** Seminars on the green iguana project at University of Bayreuth and University of Munich, Germany and the Zoological Garden of Zurich, Switzerland. (Total attendance 100).

October 20, 1989. **I. March.** "Introduction to wildlife management: history, techniques and case studies". Diplomat in conservation and management of protected natural wildlands in Latin America. La Mancha Biological Station, Veracruz, Mexico. (Attendance 20).

November 29, 1989. **J. Frazier.** "Marine turtles". Research and Advanced Studies Center, National Polytechnic Institute, Mexico. (Attendance 25).

December 11-15, 1989. **C. Vaughan.** Costa Rican Natural Resource Representative at the Programming Meeting of Multinational Projects in Science and Technology. Organization of American States. Seminar "Regional Wildlife Management Program for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean." (Attendance 26 representatives from each of 26 Western Hemisphere countries and OAS staff).

December 18, 1989. **C. Vaughan.** "The Regional Wildlife Management Program for Mesoamerica and the Caribbean". Department of Zoology, Universidad Federal de Minas Gerais, Brazil. (Attendance 15).

December 1989. **E. Vargas.** "Campesino forestry movement and the environment in Costa Rica". I Campesino Forestry Meeting. CIDESA-IUCN. San Jose, Costa Rica. (Attendance 100).

January 24-27, 1990. **I. March.** "El Ocote Ecological Reserve, Chiapas, Mexico". Meeting on Protected Wildlands Management in Southeastern Mexico. Secretary of Ecology in the Yucatan State. Mérida, Yucatan, México. (Attendance 25).

February 22, 1990. **D. Werner.** "Iguana management". Anastasio Alfaro, Science and Technology for Development Conference in CONICIT. San José, Costa Rica. (Attendance 50).

March 5-9, 1990. **C. Mo.** "Shipment and care of biological samples for virus isolation". Regional Course- Diagnostic and Epidemiology of the Important Viral Diseases in Veterinary Medicine. Heredia, Costa Rica. (Attendance 15).

April 1990. **E. Carrillo.**

"Mammals of Costa Rica with emphasis in Monteverde". Monteverde Conservationist League of Monteverde. Monteverde, Costa Rica. (Attendance 20).

Grace Wong

- June 9-23, 1990. **D. Norman**. "Wildlife management in buffer zones and obstacles that impede the potential for management of economically important species." I Mobile Workshop on Natural Resource Management in Buffer Zones of Neotropical Protected Areas. Peace University. Villa Colón, Costa Rica. (Attendance 20).
- June 12-20, 1990. **D. Werner**. Seminars on the green iguana project at the Universities of Frankfurt, Nuremberg and Hamburg and the German Academic Exchange Program in Germany; the Universities of Luzern, Basel and Zurich in Switzerland; and the Norwegian Agency for International Cooperation in Norway. (Total attendance 150).
- August 4, 1990. **C. Vaughan**. "Mesoamerican Regional Wildlife Management Program as a solution to natural resources destruction". Tropnet Group, University of Wisconsin-Madison. (Attendance 20).
- August 6-10, 1990. **M. McCoy**. Seminars on wetland restoration in Palo Verde at Fairfax Audubon Society, Organization of American States, World Wildlife Fund-US and United States Fish and Wildlife Service. Washington, D.C. (Total Attendance 100).
- September 13-14, 1990. **D. Norman**. "Rational management of wildlife". First National Youth Meeting of the Ecological Education. San José, Costa Rica. (Attendance 25).
- December 1990. **E. Vargas**. "Indigenous groups and the environment in Costa Rica". First Indigenous Forestry Meeting. CIDESIA-IUCN. San José de la Montaña, Costa Rica. (Attendance 75).
- May 18, 1991. **S. Vega**. "Pesticide use in Costa Rica". Clemson University. (Attendance 15).
- June 6, 1991. **D. Norman**. "Wildlife management to provide economic benefits for small farmers: steps to follow and common obstacles". II Mobile Workshop on Natural Resource Management in Buffer Zones of Neotropical Protected Areas. Peace University. Villa Colón, Costa Rica. (Attendance 22).
- July, 1991. **E. Vargas**. "Environmental change and acute conflict". International Workshop-Environmental Changes and Social Conflicts. University of Toronto, Canada. (Attendance 40).
- July 2, 1991. **D. Norman**. "How to distinguish poisonous from non-poisonous snakes in El Rodeo vicinity". Peace University. (Attendance 20).
- August, 1991. October, 1991. **M. Carbonell**. "Shorebird conservation". Seminar for the Costa Rican section of Inter. Council for Bird Preservation. (Attendance 13).
- September 8-13, 1991. **L. Hilje**. Biology and control of rodent pests. FAO. Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia. (Attendance 20).
- December 1991. **E. Vargas**. "Environmental problems of municipal interest. Summary of recommendations". Seminar-workshop on Local Power and Environmental Gesture. Association for the Defense of Natural Resources. Birrí, Costa Rica. (Attendance 50).
- March 24, 1992. **M. McCoy**. "Restoration of wetlands in Palo Verde Wildlife Refuge (1987-1991)". Executive Board of the Organization for Tropical Studies. Palo Verde National Park, Costa Rica. (Attendance 20).
- April 20, 1992. **H. Korn**. "Possibilities and limitations to the domestication of new animal species". Biology Faculty, University of Marburg, Germany. (Attendance 30).
- May 4-20, 1992. **D. Norman**. "Management of economically beneficial wildlife for small-scale farmers: Steps to follow and common obstacles". I Mobile Workshop on Natural Resource Management in Buffer Zones of Neotropical Protected Areas. Peace University. Villa Colón, Costa Rica. (Attendance 30).
- June 10, 1992. **C. Vaughan**. "Regional wildlife graduate programs in developing countries: organization, objectives, and importance in sustainability of natural resources". Global Forum, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. (Attendance 20).
- July 1992. **D. Norman**. "Zoogeography of Mesoamerican herpetofauna". Faculty of Exact Sciences, University of Ascension, Paraguay. (Attendance 30).
- August 6-13, 1992. Seminar. **C. Vaughan**. "GAP analysis mapping of diversity of biological resources". Office of Research/United States Agency for International Development Biodiversity Networking Meeting. Honolulu, Hawaii. (Attendance 45).
- September 25, 1992. **M. McCoy**. "Cattail eradication methods in the restoration of a freshwater, seasonal marsh in Costa Rica". Department of Botany. Southern Illinois University. Carbondale, IL. (Attendance 25).

Christopher Vaughan

"The Regional Wildlife Management Program for MesoAmerica and the Caribbean remains one of the premier elements of the Fish and Wildlife Service's Western Hemisphere program."

-Herbert A. Raffaele
Western Hemisphere Coordinator
Office of International Affairs
United States Fish and Wildlife Service
Department of the Interior
(1992)

FINANCIAL SUPPORT

FINANCIAL SUPPORT 1987-1992

Without financial assistance from both national and international agencies and from the home institution, the Universidad Nacional (UNA), PRMVS would not exist. Eighteen donors plus UNA have contributed a total of \$3,050,350 towards our efforts to become the best wildlife program in the developing world. The relative contribution of these agencies is summarized below.

These funds can be divided between 8 areas: staff salaries, student scholarships, research, general services, equipment, the wildlife documentation center (BIODOC), a student residence acquisition and overhead to the UNA

foundation (FUNA) as represented above.

It is important to note that PRMVS ensures that all students have full scholarships to enable

full-time study towards finishing their graduate training in the 27 months allotted. The United States Fish and Wildlife Service, the German Academic Exchange Program, the Jessie Smith Noyes Foundation, the World Wildlife Fund-US, and the John and Catherine MacArthur Foundation have generously provided the majority of the student scholarship funds with other organizations providing an occasional scholarship or compliment. This funding covers one round-trip airfare, living and installation allowance, registration, all course textbooks, migration, health insurance, part of thesis work and advisor field visits.

Staff salaries have been provided mostly by the Universidad Nacional, while the German

Academic Exchange Program (DAAD) has assisted the salary effort by financing German

visiting professors. Finally, the International Organization for Migrations, World Wildlife Fund-US, United States Fish and Wildlife Service, and the John and Catherine MacArthur Foundation have provided salary compensations to allow PRMVS to bring and keep quality staff.

The staff research effort has been heavily supported by the Organization of American States, World Wildlife Fund-US and the United States Fish and Wildlife Service and other organizations. The latter two organizations have contributed important funding to allow professors to travel to and participate in international conferences.

ble-cabin pick-up trucks (4-wheel drive) and one travel-all vehicle. We also have two motorcycles for student use, one 17' boat and two outboard motors. PRMVS is also well-equipped with basic field research equipment. Physical space provided by UNA includes 86 m² for administration, 107 m² for BIODOC, 167 m² for classrooms and laboratories, 56 m² for equipment storage and 80 m² for faculty offices. BIODOC has been funded by the United States Fish and Wildlife Service (\$116,000) and the Universidad Nacional.

General services (electricity, water, fax, telephone, gasoline, etc.) have been provided mostly by UNA (\$162,360), with aid of USFWS (\$12,850) and WWF-US (\$18,810).

Equipment purchases for teaching, research and vehicle maintenance have been covered by UNA (\$68,000), USFWS (\$62,478), and WWF-

In an effort to lower scholarship needs, and with United States Fish and Wildlife Service

US (\$29,212). The PRMVS now has three dou-

(\$29,757) and John and Catherine MacArthur

Foundation (\$41,500) support, PRMVS purchased a residence for the V Promotion students which accommodates seven students at present.

Finally, most international funding for PRMVS is handled by the Universidad Nacional Foundation-Omar Dengo (FUNA), which charges overhead and was paid by USFWS (\$17,526), WWF (\$6,811), and the John and Catherine MacArthur Foundation (\$5,384).

Our yearly budgets have increased over time from a low of close to \$250,000 in 1987 to a high of about \$600,000 in 1989, 1991 and 1992. Fortunately, the yearly contribution of UNA has gradually increased each year. The 1991 and 1992 contributions were each three times greater

than in 1987 and represented a third of the total yearly budget. On the other hand, our major

international funders (USFWS, WWF-US and DAAD) have recently had to cut back on their donations; the recent economic recession cited as the major cause. Because of this, there is a need to explore new funding sources, for stability in our program. The recent donations by the Jessie Smith Noyes Foundation and the John and Catherine MacArthur Foundation were timely in this regard.

Future funding needs for PRMVS include ensuring an endowment for future operations and new donors to handle student scholarships, salary compensations to attract and maintain excellent staff, new equipment, and research. To all the donors and to our home institution, we are very indebted. 🐼

We depend on your donations for continuation of our efforts in biodiversity-wildlife management in the Neotropics. This includes forming a new generation of natural resource managers, and exploring new model research and management projects and community outreach programs. We invite you or your organization to join with us in this most important endeavor and would appreciate your participation towards reaching these goals.

"Needs for wildlife and of people are inextricably linked. Conservation of the natural world for the protection and production of life which comprise it, for the processes and functions that make it work, and for the society that use it - all are at risk. Unless consideration in conservation planning is given to people and wildlife resources, no matter how noble the project or need, the plans will fail. The PRMVS is on the cutting edge of the biodiversity-wildlife management field in Latin America and is exploring ways to accommodate both the needs of people and of wildlife."

-James G. Teer, Ph.D.
Director (and ex-president of the Wildlife
Society)
Rob and Bessie Welder Wildlife Foundation
Sinton, Texas
(February, 1993)

REFLECTIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

REFLECTIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Understanding and providing technical knowledge on how to best manage and sustain natural resources in Latin America is the major mission of PRMVS. However, we also ensure that this knowledge is applied to the real world in today's increasingly complex society. Technical knowledge and biopolitics are utilized daily by staff, graduates, and students as we strive for effective environmental policies throughout Latin America.

PRMVS has broken the barrier which separated classical biology theory in Latin America from wildlife-biodiversity "hands on" conservation biology practice. In many countries, our graduates are leading these fields from their positions as university professors and researchers or from administrative and/or research positions in governmental agencies and NGOs. We have begun some of the first studies on Latin American wildlife species as theses or staff research projects, formulated management strategies for wildlife and wildlands and are involved in important outreach projects.

PRMVS and our graduates realize there are no shortcuts to intelligent natural resource management. Much research is needed, long-term positive communication with rural people and government, and publications which are utilized and not shelved. However, above all, much hard work and mysticism is needed to propose and institute economic and policy changes under generally difficult, underpaid and understimulated conditions.

Several examples of policy making come to mind. Ignacio March worked for over 5 years founding and promoting one of southern Mexico's major environmental NGOs: ECOSFERA, a watchdog for environmental quality, studies and sustainable use, especially in the Montañas Azules. Today this NGO has joined forces with several others and Ignacio forms part of an interdisciplinary team. He is responsible for implementing a GIS system in southern Mexico for environmental analysis and planning. Miguel Rodríguez is director of Costa Rica's wildlife service and after several years work, recently had a new and much improved wildlife law approved. Daniel Hernández is having part of his thesis work, a booklet on the major plant species in a neotropical marsh, published by PRMVS. Never Bonino requested assistance to publish a book on the mammals of southern Argentina. He is currently involved in teaching

graduate students (Wildlife Management Techniques and Analysis and Control of Vertebrate Pests in the new wildlife graduate program in Cordoba, Argentina. Nancy López is head of the governmental wildlife division in Paraguay. *We could go on and on!* We are very proud of the important roles these professionals are playing throughout Latin America, working with mysticism under difficult conditions.

PRMVS has evolved in many directions within the framework of the three objectives assigned in Panama in 1984, while maintaining our wildlife ecology-biodiversity focus. PRMVS stresses the real world of Latin America and teaches how decisions are made within a social, economic and political framework which our resource managers must understand and utilize to be successful. Innovative courses in Sustainable Development Theory, Conservation Biology, Rural Sociology, Environmental Education and Communication and Natural Resource Economics, and Experimental Design, as well as field courses, prepare our graduates for working in today's complex society. This is especially true in Latin American countries where our graduate may be the only professional who understands such concepts as geographical information systems, advanced statistics, corridor ecology and sustainable development theory. There isn't time to teach everything, but our wildlife conservationist is hard at work trying to save, manage and restore the biodiversity in his country.

As PRMVS advances into 1993 we will be involved in many challenges such as; reinitiating the journal, *Vida Silvestre Neotropical*, hosting the International Wildlife Management Congress, setting up a laboratory in remote sensing and GIS, bringing in a VI promotion of 18 students from 10 countries and finishing student theses in progress.

The final message: -one has to have many abilities to work in this field, in addition to a solid wildlife-biodiversity background. This includes acting as a biopolitican, visionary, communication specialist, grantwriter and ambassador. It begins with the knowledge and conviction of an excellent professional, with much of our message conveyed through example. We at PRMVS (teachers, administrators and students) are the pioneers who must point out the future and we accept the challenge. ♡

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Our students, future biologists, managers and administrators of Latin America, walk toward the future with solid skills obtained at PRMVS.

Claudette Mo

Through their participation in PRMVS we are forming a lasting network of Latin America's future leaders in conservation.

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